

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D12: CODECO Basic Operation Components and Toolkit Version 2.0

Work package	WP3 – CODECO Basic Operation components and Toolkit
Internal number	D3.2
Task	Tasks 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6
Due date	12.07.2024
Submission date	19.07.2024
Dissemination Type	Public
Deliverable leaders and editors	ICOM (Georgios Samaras, Vasileios Theodorou)
Contributing Partners	FOR (Rute C. Sofia, Dalal Ali, Hongyu Zhu); ICOM (Georgios Samaras, Maria Eleftheria Vlontzou, Konstantinos Karageorgos, Vasileios Theodorou); ATH (Lefteris Mamatas, George Koukis); SIE (Harald Mueller, Juergen Gasswein); I2CAT (Rizkallah Touma, Alejandro Espinosa); UPRC (Efterpi Paraskevoulakou, Panagiotis Karamolegkos); TID (Luis M. Contreras, Alejandro Muñiz); UC3M (Alejandro de Cock Buning, Borja Nogales, Iván Vidal, Francisco Valera), UPM (Alberto del Río, Javier Serrano, David Jimenez); RHT (Dean Kelly, Alka Nixon, Josh Salomon); IBM (Luis Garcés-Erice, Peter Urbanetz), INO (Raquel Sousa); INTRA (John Soldatos, Dorine Matzakou); ATOS (Ignacio Prusiel Mariscal);
Version	1.1
Reviewer 1	FOR (Rute C. Sofia)
Reviewer 2	ECL (David Remon)

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the Swiss Federal Government

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Project Partners

Affiliated Entities

Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Executive Summary

This report is an integral part of the CODECO deliverable **D12 - CODECO Basic Operation Components and Toolkit v2.0**. D12 consists of this report and a CODECO software release consisting of components of the CODECO open source "*Basic Operation Toolkit v2.0*", available in the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab repository](#). This open source software toolkit has been fully released in June 2024 (month 18 of CODECO) and provides the CODECO framework operational support within a K8s cluster.

D12 and the software developed is a product of the work under development in CODECO Work package 3 - *CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit* - and is a direct result of the work developed in *T3.6 - Open Edge-Cloud Toolkit Development*, the task focusing on the implementation and testing of the CODECO Toolkit based on the software components developed in Tasks 3.1 to 3.5.

Keywords: Edge-Cloud continuum; orchestration; K8s; AI/ML; network; data; compute; context-awareness.

Document Revision History:

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
v0.1	29.04.2024	Proposal for a global ToC	Georgios Samaras Konstantinos Karageorgos (ICOM)
v0.2	16.05.2024	Final assignments, updated ToC, updated header	Georgios Samaras Konstantinos Karageorgos (ICOM)
v0.5	01.06.2024	Initial contributions	All partners
v0.7	16.06.2024	Updated figures, format agreed	All partners
v0.8	28.06.2024	Contributions from partners before interval review	All partners
v0.8	29.06.2024	Contributions, editing and formatting	Georgios Samaras, Konstantinos Karageorgos (ICOM)
v0.9	01.07.2024	Comments addressed, contributions	Josh Salomon, Ray Carrol (RHT), Efterpi Paraskevoulakou, Panagiotis Karamolegkos (UPRC), Georgios Koukis, Lefteris Mamatras, Vassilis Tsaoussidis (ATH)
v1.0	04.07.2024	Revision by internal reviewer ECL	David Remon (ECL)
v1.1	05.07.2024	Revision by internal reviewer FOR	Rute C. Sofia (FOR)
v1.2	15.07.2024	Integration of additional content by partners	Georgios Samaras Konstantinos Karageorgos (ICOM)
v1.3	16.07.2024	Revision by FOR	Rute C. Sofia (FOR)
v1.4	17.07.2024	Revision by ECL	David Remon (ECL)
v1.0	18.07.2024	Release to Coordinator	Georgios Samaras (ICOM)
v1.1	19.07.2024	Submission to the EC	Rute C. Sofia (FOR)

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable have been developed by the Horizon Europe CODECO project consortium, under the European Union grant Agreement number 101092696. The content does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice: © 2023 - 2025 CODECO Consortium

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Document Scope	9
1.2 Dependencies	10
1.3 Document Structure	10
2 CODECO Architecture Overview and Workflow Examples	10
2.1 Component-Oriented Architecture Perspective	13
2.2 CODECO OSS Toolkit Workflow Examples	15
2.2.1 Creating an Application Deployment with CODECO	15
2.2.2 CODECO Support during Cluster Runtime	16
3 CODECO Components Specification and Implementation	17
3.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management	18
3.1.1 Component Description	18
3.1.2 The CODECO Application Model	22
3.1.3 Using CAM to Deploy and Monitor Applications	23
3.1.4 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation and Integration	24
3.1.5 ACM Code Open Issues	26
3.2 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness	27
3.2.1 Component Description	27
3.2.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation, and Integration	28
3.2.3 PDLC Code Open Issues	48
3.3 NetMA: Network Management and Adaptation	49
3.3.1 Component Description	49
3.3.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation and Integration	50
3.3.3 NetMA Code Open Issues	61
3.4 MDM: Metadata Manager	61
3.4.1 Component Description	61
3.4.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation and Integration	62
3.5 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration	73
3.5.1 Component description	73
3.5.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation and Integration	75
3.5.3 SWM Open Issues	82
4 Experimentation Assisted Developments	83
4.1 CODECO Synthetic Data Generator	83
4.1.1 Component Description	83
4.1.2 Specification and Implementation Aspects	83
4.2 Facility Porting Artefacts	84
4.2.1 CODEF: CODECO Experimentation Framework	84
5 Continuous Integration, Testing, Deployment Preparation and Releasing	90
5.1 Application Workloads	90
5.1.1 CODECO Dummy Application Workload	90
5.1.2 CODECO Use-case P5 Application Workload	91
5.2 Testing, Deployment Preparation and Releasing	91
5.2.1 Deployment and CI/CD Methodology	93
5.2.2 Integration and Testing Facilities	95
6 Summary and Next Steps	96
7 References	97
Annex I – Summary of Code Open Issues	98
Annex II – Release Versioning	99

List of Figures

Figure 1: Functional representation of the CODECO framework and its components.....	12
Figure 2: The CODECO reference architecture, single cluster operation [2].....	14
Figure 3: User-story 2: deployment of an application via CODECO.....	16
Figure 4: CODECO sequence diagram, Basic OSS Toolkit operation during cluster run-time.	17
Figure 5: ACM and sub-components.	19
Figure 6: Logic representation of the CAM.	23
Figure 7: PDLC sub-components and interfaces [2].	28
Figure 8: Main interactions between the PDLC sub-components.	28
Figure 9: PDLC-DP Gatherer module internal functionality.....	29
Figure 10: PDLC-DP Gatherer module's Cluster Sample Schema.	30
Figure 11: PDLC-DP preprocessing module subcomponent internal functionality.	31
Figure 12: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-DP.....	33
Figure 13: UML Sequence diagram of PDLC-CA.	37
Figure 14: Internal architecture of the PDLC-GNN sub-component.	38
Figure 15: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-GNN.....	41
Figure 16: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-RL.	45
Figure 17: MLOps pipeline depicting the retraining integration with PDLC-GNN.	46
Figure 18: The workflow operations of the MLOps pipeline for PDLC-GNN.....	46
Figure 19: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-MLOps.	48
Figure 20: NetMA and its sub-components.	50
Figure 21: Flow-chart of the sub-component netma-nsm-npp.	52
Figure 22: netma-nsm-mon flow-chart.....	54
Figure 23: Nemesys workflow diagram.....	56
Figure 24: Secure Connectivity Design.	58
Figure 25: MDM sub-components and APIs to other components.....	62
Figure 26: Interaction between MDM subcomponents.....	68
Figure 27: SWM high-level representation.	74
Figure 28: SWM QoS-Scheduler subcomponent structure.	75
Figure 29: Interaction between Solver's components and Scheduler.	81
Figure 30: SWM Solver's package relationships.	82
Figure 32: CODECO Use-case P5 Application Workload.....	91
Figure 33: Deployed K8s pods.	93
Figure 34: Deployed Pods in K8s.....	94

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

List of Tables

Table 1: ACM interfaces to other CODECO components.....	19
Table 2: Application Metrics.....	21
Table 3: Service Metrics.....	21
Table 4: Node Metrics.....	21
Table 5: CODECO ACM code structure.....	24
Table 6: ACM code open issues.....	26
Table 7: Status of PDLC interfaces to other CODECO components.....	28
Table 8: PDLC-DP preprocessing operations for each of the PDLC subcomponents.....	31
Table 9: Description of the main PDLC-DP source code files.....	31
Table 10: PDLC-DP Output to Corresponding subcomponents.....	33
Table 11: Summary of main PDLC-CA source code files.....	35
Table 12: Description of the main PDLC-GNN source code files.....	39
Table 13: Description of the main PDLC-RL source code files.....	42
Table 14: Inputs and outputs of PDLC-RL.....	44
Table 15: Description of the main PDLC MLOps source code files.....	46
Table 16: PDLC code open Issues.....	48
Table 17: Description of the main netma-nsm-npp source code files.....	51
Table 18: Description of the main netma-nsm-mon source code files.....	52
Table 19: Nemesys source code files.....	55
Table 20: Configuration parameters in Nemesys.....	57
Table 21: Nemesys Input & Output.....	58
Table 22: NetMA's Integration Open Issues.....	61
Table 23: Description of the main MDM GraphDB source code files.....	63
Table 24: Description of the main MDM Controller source code files.....	64
Table 25: Description of the main MDM API source code files.....	64
Table 26: Main MDM K8s connector source code files.....	70
Table 27: Description of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.....	71
Table 28: Description of the main MDM K8s connector source code files.....	72
Table 29: SWM QoS-Scheduler code structure (Go packages).....	77
Table 30: Packages and files in Solver's module.....	81
Table 31: SWM Open-source code issues.....	82
Table 31: Description of the main CODECO Experimentation framework source code files.....	85
Table 32: Status of the CODECO proposed integration and testing facilities.....	95
Table 36: CODECO OSS Basic Operation Toolkit v2.0, summary of open issues.....	98
Table 37: CODECO sub-components.....	99

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Manager
AD	Anomaly Detection
AD	Anomaly Detection
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTO	Application-Layer Traffic Optimization
API	Application Programming Interface
APOC	Awesome Procedures on Cypher
ARM	Advanced RISC Machines
CA	Context-awareness
CAM	CODECO Application Model
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CP	Change Point
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/ Continuous Deployment
CLI	Command Line Interface
CNI	Container Network Interface
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CODEF	CODECO Experimentation Framework
CP	Change Point
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
CSDG	CODECO Synthetic Data Generator
DEV	Developer
DL	Decentralised Learning
DL	Deep Learning
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter
EC	European Commission
FIDO	Fast Identity Online
GNNs	Graph Neural Networks
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Horizon Europe
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
IP	Internet Protocol
IPAM	IP Address Management
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
K8s	K8s
KCP	K8s like Control Plane
KFP	Kubeflow Pipelines
KinD	K8s in Docker
L2	Layer 2
L2S-M	Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms
LPM	L2S-M Performance Measurements
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
MDM	Metadata Manager
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MGT	Infrastructure Manager

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Acronym	Meaning
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
NSM	Network State Monitoring
OAS	Open API Specification
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OS	Operating System
OSS	Open-Source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
PPO	Proximal Policy Optimization
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
REST	Representational State Transfer
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SDG	Synthetic Data Generator
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Network
STGNN	Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network
VM	Virtual Machine
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

Acknowledgements

We thank all CODECO Partners involved in Work Package 3 for the commitment and involvement in the development of Deliverable D12.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

1 Introduction

The Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration (CODECO) Deliverable *D12 – CODECO Basic Operation Components and Toolkit v2.0* corresponds to an update to the CODECO Deliverable D11 (CODECO Basic Operation Toolkit v1.0 and companion report) [1] and describes the specification and implementation of the CODECO basic operation (all components). D12 comprises the CODECO Open-Source Software (OSS) Basic Toolkit available via the CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research project¹, along with this report. The overall deliverable corresponds to the final CODECO release v2.0 for intra-cluster operation, thus updating the code that has been uploaded in month 10 (M10) of CODECO to its Eclipse GitLab.

This specific report targets the CODECO stakeholder group DEV (Developers).

Deliverable D12 is a result of the work developed in *Work Package 3 (WP3)* from M1 to M18. focuses on the development of the CODECO framework and its components, covering specification, implementation and testing. The CODECO basic operation concerns the different proposed modules that can assist the development of a flexible, cognitive and self-organizing Edge-Cloud based on a single cluster environment.

In WP3, Tasks 3.1 to 3.5 handle the CODECO components and respective interfacing to other CODECO components and to the user as defined in D10. Task 3.6 handles the overall system integration, being a task that is orthogonal to all WP3 tasks. Hence, D12 covers the work developed in WP3, focusing on the on the implementation and testing of the CODECO toolkit, based on the software components under development across Tasks 3.1 to 3.5, coordinated by T3.6.

The work presented in D12 has been based on an Agile methodology, where CODECO components and their sub-components have been developed while the CODECO architecture was being defined (rf. to D10, released in M18 [2]).

D12 aim is two-fold. Firstly, to facilitate the development, integration, and deployment of the CODECO framework following an incremental approach, which will allow to coordinate the work of the consortium members belonging to different organisations as well as external developers, as CODECO offers open-source code, and reduce the complexity of the project. Secondly, to allow access by developers to the second (final) release of the CODECO OSS Basic toolkit, following the guidelines for the development of a robust open-source community.

1.1 Document Scope

D12 holds, as explained, a final version of the open-source CODECO Basic Operation Toolkit, and an explanation of its software design. This deliverable provides:

- An explanation on the CODECO integration framework and implementation procedures for the CODECO Basic Operation Toolkit.
- A description of tools adopted to support the defined implementation workflow; coding guidelines that may optimize the developer's coding effort and time, installation instructions, and tools/ programming languages used as the basis for technology development in the context of the CODECO project.

¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

D12 is composed of the following parts:

- This report (software companion report).
- The second (final) release of the CODECO Basic Operation Toolkit available via the [CODECO Eclipse Gitlab](#).

1.2 Dependencies

D12 has the following dependencies:

- D10 - CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design last version. D10 [2] provides the overall CODECO reference architecture and covers technological boundaries and best practices being used in CODECO.

1.3 Document Structure

This report is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** introduces the overall deliverable scope, structure, and components.
- **Section 2** provides a summary of the CODECO architectural design and highlights the sub-components that are being released in this deliverable.
- **Section 3** provides the companion reporting for the use of the existing code, detailed per sub-component.
- **Section 4** covers additional software artifacts, such as data generators, which have been developed to assist the use of CODECO.
- **Section 5** describes the continuous system testing and the deployment framework that has been set in T3.6 to assist the overall project, as well as the continuous integration and released version of each subcomponent/feature developed in the second implementation cycle of CODECO.
- **Section 6** concludes the document, presenting next steps for the next phase of development of the CODECO OSS Toolkits.
- **Annex I** provides a list of code open issues.
- **Annex II** provides the release versioning per component and sub-component.

2 CODECO Architecture Overview and Workflow Examples

This section provides a summary of the CODECO single cluster architectural framework design described in detail in deliverable D10. The aim is to assist the reader in understanding the design choices that led to the software described in this deliverable. Hence, details on the architectural design, components, and interfacing across CODECO are available with more detail in D10 [1] and are therefore not repeated in this deliverable. The terminology adopted, compatible with K8s² (K8s), has already been described in D10.

CODECO is a containerised application orchestration framework (Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4-5), independent and yet pluggable to K8s (K8s). CODECO aims at providing support for a flexible and cognitive *Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI)* infrastructure. The notion of infrastructure in CODECO considers different infrastructure perspectives: the **networking** perspective, where the network is perceived both as the *underlay* and *overlay* infrastructure required to support the deployment of containerised applications across CEI; the **data**

² <https://K8s.io/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

observability perspective, bringing input on the data dependencies that micro-services may have, and that is important to consider during the application deployment and re-deployment; the **computational** perspective, bringing input on the suitable nodes to serve an application, taking into consideration. CODECO addresses the orchestration across these three different perspectives in an integrated approach, which is named as **data-compute-network** orchestration.

As a cognitive and decentralised orchestration framework, CODECO embraces a next generation vision where data and services are stored and computed across the Internet whole-chain, in a holistic cooperation between Cloud and far Edge [4]. Components of containerised applications, which in CODECO are addressed as *micro-services*, reside in isolated, self-sufficient containers, which can be deployed and executed in any underlying environment. A flexible and secure networking infrastructure provides adaptable interconnection that adapt to the needs and the surrounding environment of the services being run.

Relevant in CODECO is an adaptation based on application requirements and user requirements. A functional representation of CODECO and its open-source components is provided in Figure 1. The initial design of container orchestrators contemplated a Cloud-based deployment. However, with the increasing move of data storage, processing and analysis to the so-called *far Edge*, applications and their micro-services can be scattered across mobile, often constrained environments. Based on this functional level, CODECO offers the following aspects:

- **Automated configuration**, focusing on supporting application setup and application runtime across Edge-Cloud, by taking into consideration compute, network, and data aspects. The key aspects of this contribution are supported by the CODECO *Advanced Configuration and Management (ACM)* component.
- **Data as a resource**. CODECO addresses, via its *Metadata Manager (MDM)* component data as a resource in the sense that available snapshots from the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure, integrating different perspectives (application, user, system, data, network) at different instants of the CODECO operational workflow can be provided to different CODECO components, to assist in detecting relevant changes.
- **Dynamic scheduling and workload migration**. Supported by the CODECO component *Scheduling and Workload Migration (SWM)*, CODECO brings in novel *Quality of Service (QoS)* models that consider data-network-compute requirements to provide a best match between applications and available infrastructure (nodes, their computational and data properties, as well as network nodes and links), and to schedule and re-schedule application workloads across single cluster and federated cluster environments, considering application and user requirements.
- **Context-awareness and privacy preserving decentralised learning**. CODECO relies on context-awareness to be able to achieve a joint data-network-compute orchestration, and on privacy-preserving decentralised learning and inference to best support readjustment of aspects such as the processing capability, computational resources, networking resources and interconnections in real-time. Context-awareness and decentralised learning are part of the CODECO *Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning (PDLC)* component.
- **Infrastructure adaptation based on a cross-layer data-compute-network approach**. Via the CODECO *Network Management and Adaptation component (NetMA)*, CODECO assists in adapting not just computational (node resources) but also the networking infrastructure interconnecting such nodes, having as starting point for the exposure of metadata within one cluster and across federated clusters, from far Edge to Cloud.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 1: Functional representation of the CODECO framework and its components.

The only interface of CODECO to the user, as shown in Figure 1, is the ACM component, which focuses on supporting application setup and runtime from the far Edge to the Cloud, considering the input provided by the user.

The user in CODECO is perceived as an **application developer (DEV)** or as a **cluster manager (MGT)**.

To setup CODECO, a user relies on the CODECO framework. ACM installs the entire CODECO framework, handling the overall CODECO configuration. The user can specify, via the **CODECO Application Model (CAM)**, the requirements of the application and of its micro-services. These requirements are relevant to allow CODECO to deploy the application across CEI in an efficient way.

Via CAM, the user specifies also **target performance profiles** that CODECO should meet during its operation, e.g., a specific level of **greenness**, or **resilience**.

Once CODECO is installed, all CODECO components can be used. The CODECO components have been devised to allow each component to work independently, with other future open orchestration frameworks, requiring little adaptation.

The **CODECO MDM** component provides data workflow observability to the other CODECO components, treating data as an integral part of the application workload, and integrating data observability perspectives from different categories, e.g., application perspective, system perspective, network perspective, at different points in the CODECO operational workflow.

SWM handles the scheduling and rescheduling of the application workload, based on the CAM supported by ACM and provided by the user during application setup, thus integrating the novel data-compute-network approach proposed by CODECO.

The currently available approach for handling placement decisions relies on a graph-based optimization approach which in contrast to the K8s filtering and score approach is expected to provide an optimal match between application requirements and available resources

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

(computational, network, data). SWM is also a control plane component, co-located with ACM and the K8s control plane, in master nodes.

PDLC is at the heart of the CODECO orchestration. Based on the infrastructure data collected by ACM (via Prometheus), NetMA, and MDM, PDLC has two functions. Firstly, it provides an aggregated cost view of a specific target performance profile for the available infrastructure which can be used by other components and is currently being considered in SWM to further define the optimal workload placement. Secondly, it provides an estimate on the overall system stability based on privacy-preserving decentralised learning approaches. PDLC is currently envisaged to operate on both K8s master and worker nodes.

NetMA provides the network awareness to CODECO and handles also secure connectivity across Pods. For this purpose, NetMA **collects and exposes networking metrics** that are relevant to do an optimal workload placement. NetMA provides in addition **secure connectivity** via Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms (**L2S-M³**). Hence, NetMA is a component responsible for interconnecting the *Software-defined Networking (SDN)* world with K8s.

To be able to achieve a flexible orchestration, **CODECO counts with monitoring across the three different CEI infrastructure perspectives**. NetMA monitors the networking infrastructure; MDM monitors the data infrastructure; ACM monitors the system (computational nodes) infrastructure based on the K8s metrics server Prometheus⁴. This approach allows to explore the integration of new metrics as well as of providing the collected metrics of CODECO to future orchestration frameworks.

The CODECO framework is deployed as an application: each CODECO component is based on a modular approach, integrating different sub-components that are expected to be built as one or more independent (dockerized) micro-services.

2.1 Component-Oriented Architecture Perspective

A component-oriented perspective of the CODECO architecture is illustrated in Figure 2 considering the CODECO operation within a single cluster deployment⁵. For the representation provided in the Figure and for all subsequent component descriptions, a few considerations are here summarized to assist the reader of this deliverable:

- **I-comp1-comp2-X** describes components from CODECO component one to CODECO component two. For instance, I-MDM-PDLC-1 means that an interface from MDM to PDLC of type *Input*, *Output*, or *bi-directional* is being conceived.
- **The high-level interfaces between CODECO components** are illustrated in strong, dashed green lines.
- **Internal interfaces** between sub-components are represented via light, dashed, black lines.
- **Interfaces to external entities**, e.g., user, non-K8s systems are represented via a grey, solid line.

³ <http://l2sm.io>

⁴ <https://prometheus.io/>

⁵ The architectural design of CODECO is being developed taking into consideration challenges related with an operation across federated clusters. However, the CODECO framework support for federated clusters environment has been planned under WP4, which will be active from M19 until M36 of the project.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 2: The CODECO reference architecture, single cluster operation [2].

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

2.2 CODECO OSS Toolkit Workflow Examples

This section aims to provide the reader with the latest updates on the CODECO OSS Toolkit operational workflow within a single K8s cluster. For this, two specific user stories are presented next.

2.2.1 Creating an Application Deployment with CODECO

User Story 1 – CODECO Framework Installation

DEV is a user deploying an application consisting of multiple micro-services (multiple Docker images) across the far Edge to the Cloud. DEV has already created a cluster according to an initial estimation of the application's needs. DEV downloads CODECO from the CODECO Eclipse GitLab and follows the instructions to set up ACM. The CAM is a file based on the scheme of *Yet Another Markup Language (YAML)* which is provided to user DEV during application deployment setup. In this file, user DEV defines aspects such as desired *Quality of Service (QoS)*, *Quality of Experience (QoE)*, or other desired performance levels for CODECO, based on specific questions provided in a future ACM Web-based *User Interface (UI)*. The attributes considered in the CAM are represented in Figure 6. A full description of all attributes considered can be found in D10, Annex I.

Based on the specific parameters (representing the application requirements), ACM builds the CAM and makes it available to all CODECO components.

ACM also manages the complete K8s setup (e.g., namespace, databases, secrets) and makes the information available to other K8s components as needed. For example, metadata information, schema, can be passed to MDM (I-ACM-MDM-2). Application requirements derived from the CAM, e.g., dedicated *Central Processing Unit (CPU)* or required bandwidth, are made available to SWM (I-ACM-SWM-1) and to PDLC (I-ACM-PDLC-1), for instance.

User Story 2 – Deployment of an application via CODECO

The exposure of requirements and application/user information also triggers the operation of each CODECO component. PDLC handles the computing of aggregated node costs based on target performance profiles provided in CAM and the required AI/ML estimation for the infrastructure and application. SWM makes an initial application workload placement based on metrics available in CODECO at a computational (provided by ACM) and networking level (provided by NetMA). Updates to this initial scheduling will be updated later based on node recommendations by PDLC. NetMA triggers the definition of the network overlay when it receives the initial deployment from SWM (I-SWM-NET-1).

After activation, PDLC regularly obtains, via available CRDs (I-ACM-PDLC-1,2), metadata provided by MDM (data metrics), ACM (user aspects and application constrains, i.e., the CAM), NetMA (network metrics). PDLC performs an initial multi-level objective estimation based on the user selected target profiles defined in CAM, and stores the output on a PDLC CRD, making it available to ACM, which may trigger adjustments to the initial setup process. PDLC also writes the computed node recommendations on an SWM CR, which SWM then takes into consideration for the application deployment process.

In parallel, three components start monitoring different metrics: NetMA captures network metrics at node, link and path level, and exposes this information via specific CRs that are accessible to all components and used by PDLC and ACM. Similarly, MDM captures data aspects (e.g., data compliance), generates a knowledge graph and provides the output as well

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

to other components via the MDM API. ACM captures user preferences and eventually behaviour, which may be useful for adapting the overall K8s infrastructure at a later stage.

The deployment process of an application by relying on CODECO is represented in Figure 3.

Currently the communication between components takes place through K8s CRDs, so K8s plays an important role in the whole process, but we chose to omit it from the sequence diagram for readability purposes. However, note that the exchange of important metrics between components is assisted by Prometheus, in interconnection with the ACM component.

Figure 3: User-story 2: deployment of an application via CODECO.

2.2.2 CODECO Support during Cluster Runtime

Once the setup is complete, CODECO enters the cluster management phase (application runtime support), targeting the user Infrastructure Manager (MGT). During this phase, the proposed application has been set up and is running on several Docker containers which are distributed across one or more K8s pods per worker node. PDLC periodically checks the data monitored by MDM (I-MDM-PDLC-1), by NetMA and by ACM (I-ACM-PDLC-1). Furthermore, PDLC gets information on the performed assignment from SWM regarding the placement of the application workload (I-SWM-PDLC-1).

Based on this, PDLC periodically evaluates the proposed system performance targets (e.g., greenness, service latency) provided by DEV during application setup, and provides a cost combination per infrastructure element via a CR (I-PDLC-ACM-2).

If there is a need for cross-layer redistribution of the application workload, this step triggers a request from ACM to all CODECO components.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

The node recommendations computed by SWM are periodically provided via a specific CR to SWM (I-PDLC-SWM-2). Hence, if re-scheduling occurs, the respective SWM CR Assignment Plan is accessible to PDLC (I-SWM-PDLC-1).

At the current stage of deployment, it is highlighted that the re-scheduling process in CODECO is not yet implemented in SWM. This feature will be completed until M24 of the project as mentioned in the list of SWM code open issues, section 4.5.3.

ACM provides, via CAM, the status to the user MGT. These steps are represented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: CODECO sequence diagram, Basic OSS Toolkit operation during cluster run-time.

3 CODECO Components Specification and Implementation

This section provides an overview concerning the CODECO components specification based on the deliverable D10 and derived from the initial eighteen months of the project. The aim is to describe the components, their inputs and outputs, their pre-requisites, as well as their functionalities provided in alignment with the current code release (June 2024).

The description here provided corresponds to a low-level specification of the components for which the following details are provided:

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- **Component Description:** describes how each sub-component is implemented, including workflows, data structures and any other relevant information.
- **Sub-components specification and implementation description:** a brief description of the main source code files of the sub-component. This considers:
 - **Code Structure,** basic description, and links to the main source code files.
 - **Pre-requisites:** Pre-requisites required to deploy and evaluate the sub-component in terms of infrastructure, software, libraries, etc.
 - **Installation guide:** describes the steps that need to be followed to deploy and evaluate the subcomponent and includes links to all relevant readme and config files.
 - **Inputs and outputs** summarize the input and output formats of the sub-component.
 - **UML sequence diagrams:** representation of the sub-components and their interactions.
- **Code Open Issues.** Summary of main aspects to be solved still in the CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit v2.0 release.

All the code described is available as docker images via the [CODECO dockerHub repository, hecodeco](#).

3.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management

3.1.1 Component Description

ACM provides methodologies, based on cutting-edge technologies, and next generation tooling which supports automatic configuration, secure monitoring/data transfer between components, and federated cluster configuration and deployment across the Edge-Cloud continuum, for both single and multi-cluster environments. This community-driven and open-source process is based on a version of Red Hat's ACM (Advanced Cluster Manager), and its upstream Open Cluster Manager (OCM).

CODECO ACM is built as a K8s plugin and is based on a series of K8s operators, both custom and established, working together. The security aspect, which ACM also considers, focuses on attack mitigation and detection across distributed environments.

To deploy ACM, and in turn the entire CODECO framework, user DEV needs access to a running K8s or Openshift cluster. User DEV must also have an image registry set up somewhere like [hub.docker.io](https://hub.docker.com/)⁶ or quay.io⁷. By following the instructions provided in the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab for the component ACM](#), user DEV will be guided on building his own image and deploying ACM through that. After some time, all five component repositories will be installed on user DEV's cluster and their pods will start to create and run on his cluster automatically. The CODECO consortium focused on making this process as streamlined and easy for the user as possible and succeeded by allowing CODECO's infrastructure to be created through no more than three commands. In the next phase, all CODECO components will be added to a permanent registry, saving the user the need to build the system from the source code. The entire source code of ACM is available under [ACM](#), in the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research project](#).

6 <https://hub.docker.com/>

7 <https://quay.io/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 5Error! Reference source not found. depicts ACM and its sub-components as well as existing interfaces [2], which are described in Table 1.

Figure 5: ACM and sub-components.

Table 1: ACM interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-ACM-PROM	Integration of the CODECO metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-MDM-1	Data collection from CRDs of other components, to be used in the MDM integration of the CODECO MDM operator.	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-PDLC-1	Integration of CA derived metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Input
I-ACM-PDLC-2	Use of CRDs from other components by PDLC	CRD	Output
I-ACM-NET-1	Integration of the NetMA CRD/CR(s) and respective operator(s)	CRD	Input
I-ACM-SWM-1	Integration of the SWM controller-manager (CRD/CR(s) via K8s API)	CR via K8s API (REST)	Bi-directional

The approach taken in CODECO is to rely on and extend existing OSS technologies in order to deliver the features required to support an agile and highly interoperable CODECO framework. The ACM initial sub-components, illustrated in Figure 3 are:

- **OCM⁸**: This project is the basis for ACM and is used to enable end-to-end visibility and control across multiple K8s clusters. It will be used to provide the main ACM functionality and extended to provide special support and visibility of the CODECO components and applications. For the single cluster implementation of CODECO OCM was not used as it is relevant to the application in federated clusters (rf. to WP4).
- **Monitoring**: New metrics integrated into Prometheus⁹. Different CODECO components (ACM, NetMA, MDM) collect parameters that shall assist in a more flexible schedule, with compute, network, and data awareness. The CODECO components collecting input shall monitor specific parameters and report some of the data (slow paced) in CRs. The CODECO component PDLC handles, via its sub-component PDLC-CA, the creation of new aggregated node metrics from the collected parameters. ACM monitoring shall therefore be a sub-component that shall articulate the monitoring across the different components and proposes a coordinated integration into Prometheus. The new CODECO CRDs can be extended to, among other functionalities, specify how groups of K8s services or pods should be monitored or to specify scrape configurations to be added to Prometheus. Built-in K8s metrics can also be enhanced by gathering more information with the use of node exporters or *extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF)* hooks, like

8 <https://github.com/open-cluster-management-io/ocm>

9 <https://github.com/prometheus/prometheus>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Kepler¹⁰, that relies on eBPF to probe energy-related system stats and exports them as Prometheus metrics.

- **Control plane for independent/isolated clusters.** There are multiple open-source technologies that handle this problem (for example, *K8s like Control Plane (KCP*¹¹*)*) and it is yet to be decided which technology to use for this problem. Here, the aim is to consider mobile environments where intermittent connectivity may prevent the registration of a cluster to the OCM Hub. An example relates with the use of clusters involving mobile devices, such as cars (rf. to D8 use-case P2, Smart Cities [5]), or *Automated Guided Vehicles* (rf. To D8 use-case P5, Manufacturing).
- **Far Edge integration,** via lightweight K8s distributions. CODECO addresses the support of clusters involving embedded devices at the far Edge, potentially mobile. Hence, ACM considers the integration and interoperability to manage lightweight support via solutions such as K3s¹², Microshift¹³.
- **Secure deployment.** The secure onboarding of new cyber-physical systems at the Edge is handled via ACM, based on tools such as *Fast Identity Online (FIDO*¹⁴*)* and *Trusted Execution Environment (TEE*¹⁵*)*.
- **Hierarchical control plane.** Via Hypershift¹⁶, ACM supports a separation of the control plane into a centralised cluster (Cloud or Edge), considering that remote worker nodes are being deployed at the Edge.
- All the technologies that are mentioned above for managing federated environment deployment (OCM, KCP, far Edge integration, Hypershift) are not implemented as part of the single cluster deployment, as they will be used in federated clusters (rf. to WP4).

3.1.1.1 Configuration

ACM has streamlined the integration of CODECO's components by creating an automated installation process which deploys the ACM K8s operator and, in turn, deploys the other components with minimal effort for the user. ACM considers the installation of all other operators and their Pre-requisites by creating two scripts which will run during ACM's deployment. The pre-deploy script¹⁷ will install all necessary component repositories. There is also functionality to ensure they do not install twice if the repos have already been manually installed. The post deploy script¹⁸ then enters each repository and configures and deploys the components on the cluster.

3.1.1.2 Cluster Configuration

Currently, CODECO relies on a single cluster deployment. This cluster needs to have specific configuration to suit all component pre-requisites. The configuration includes a master node, and two workers labelled c1 and c2, meaning there are three nodes in total. Although at this stage the architecture can support any number of workers, the minimum requirement for the components is three, with these specific labels in which components will then seek to reference and send their data to. This minimal cluster is specifically designed and configured for developers that want to run CODECO on their local machine using K8s in Docker (KinD¹⁹).

10 <https://github.com/sustainable-computing-io/kepler?tab=readme-ov-file#kepler>

11 <https://github.com/kcp-dev/kcp#-kcp>

12 <https://k3s.io/>

13 <https://github.com/openshift/microshift?tab=readme-ov-file#microshift>

14 <https://fido-alliance.github.io/how-to-fido/HowToFIDO.html>

15 <https://globalplatform.org/specs-library/?filter-committee=tee>

16 <https://github.com/openshift/hypershift?tab=readme-ov-file#hypershift>

17 https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm/-/blob/rht-integration/scripts/pre_deploy.sh

18 https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm/-/blob/rht-integration/scripts/post_deploy.sh

19 <https://kind.sigs.k8s.io/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Applying the [kind-config.yaml](#) file to the cluster brings up the cluster with this tailored configuration.

Currently, CODECO partners are using individual clusters with different configurations (rf. to D10 for guidelines on requirements). Furthermore, CODECO is setting up a shared Cloud space that can be used by all partners (interconnected to individual clusters, or not). Hence, the current development of the CODECO OSS Toolkit takes into consideration the requirements proposed in D10 and focuses on a single cluster operation, being prepared to easily adapt to multi-cluster environments, including far Edge devices such as embedded devices, and single node K8s (such as MicroShift²⁰ or k3s²¹).

3.1.1.3 Monitoring

CODECO considers a monitoring functionality to ACM which will provides user DEV and user MGT with both pod level information and general system metrics in the CAM **status** field. These metrics correspond to the **CODECO monitored metrics** which bring a perspective of the Edge-Cloud infrastructure based on the CODECO **data-compute-network** approach (rf. to D10).

Table 2, Table 3, Table 4 provide examples on the selected metrics in use – a full definition of metrics is presented in Annex I (derived from D10). Specifically, Table 2 provides examples for metrics at an Application level; Table 3 provides an example of metrics at a **micro-service** level (captured at a K8s pod level); and Table 4 of metrics monitored at a node level.

Note: For the rest of section 3.1 the term *service* refers to micro-service as defined by CODECO architecture and should not be confused with K8s service.

Table 2: Application Metrics.

Metric	Description
avgAppCpu	Aggregation of the CPU usage of all the services in the app (in vCPU units)
avgAppMemory	Aggregation of the memory usage of all the services in the app
numPods	The number of the pods instantiated for the application

Table 3: Service Metrics.

Metric	Description
avgServiceCpu	Average CPU usage per micro service pod
avgServiceMemory	Average memory usage per micro service pod
clusterName	Cluster name (unique, assigned by K8s)
nodeName	Node name (unique, assigned by K8s)
podName	Pod name (unique, assigned by K8s)
serviceName	Service name, user assigned in the app model, non-unique (can have multiple instances of the same service)

Table 4: Node Metrics.

Metric	Description
avgNodeCpu	Avg CPU consumption of the application on this node (aggregation of service CPU over the node)
avgNodeEnergy	Avg energy consumption of the node
avgNodeFailure	node failures averaged over a specific time window (Exponential moving average)

²⁰ <https://github.com/openshift/microshift?tab=readme-ov-file#microshift>

²¹ <https://k3s.io/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

avgNodeMemory	Avg memory consumption of the application on this node (aggregation of service memory over the node)
nodeName	Node name (unique, assigned by K8s)

The CAM status monitoring is implemented through functionality in the reconcile loop of the CODECO ACM operator. The ACM operator runs periodically (every minute) even when there are no changes to the CRs, and each time it runs it updates the status fields of the CR. This means that these metrics change infrequently (once a minute) and are suitable only for coarse grain statistics.

All the metrics data is stored in Prometheus, and it is possible to easily create additional views on the data via rules that are defined in a Prometheus rule YAML file. An example of [Prometheus rule](#) file can be found in the public repository (rf. to [ACM/prom_rules](#)).

Component developers can then put this YAML file into a specified directory, which is then volume mounted in a Dockerfile. These rules are automatically applied to the CODECO cluster through code in ACM. Then, using Grafana or any other tool that can read from Prometheus, it is possible to query and retrieve data, displaying the requested metrics graphically. Querying Prometheus is the way to get fine grained metrics on the platform and the applications. An example of querying Prometheus using the [PromQL protocol is available in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab](#).

3.1.2 The CODECO Application Model

The [CAM](#), illustrated in Figure 6, is an extension to the K8s pod-based model designed to manage and monitor distributed, multi-pod applications as a whole, emphasising both specification and status aspects. The Application entity forms the core of the model, encapsulating detailed specifications through the *AppSpec* class, which includes parameters like application name, quality of service, security, compliance, energy limits and data size requirements. Each application can consist of multiple services (micro-services in CODECO), defined by the *ServiceSpec* class, detailing resource usage at a computational (e.g., CPU, memory), network (e.g., latency, bandwidth, energy spent during transmission), and data (e.g., freshness, age of information) level. The CAM is an augmentation of the single-cluster pod-based model of K8s into multi-cluster multi-pod application model which controls and manages various application dimensions together as a single CRD entity.

Each micro-service is implemented as a pod. Communication between micro-services is facilitated by the *Channel* and *AdvancedChannelSettings* classes, which outline the communication pathways and additional channel configurations. The *PodSpec* class links services to K8s pod specifications, ensuring deployment consistency. On the status side, the *AppStatus* class aggregates runtime metrics, captured in the *AppStatusMetrics* class, e.g., pod count, memory and CPU usage, network load, and associated costs. The model also includes *NodeStatusMetrics* to monitor node-specific performance and reliability, and *ServiceStatusMetrics* to track service-level metrics on nodes. This structure allows for detailed, hierarchical monitoring and management of applications, ensuring efficient resource utilisation, performance tracking, and compliance adherence across distributed systems.

Figure 6 shows the CAM in detail. It defines various specifications for applications, services, and channels, while it also outlines the metrics for assessing the status and performance of these entities. The structure supports the aggregation of metrics at multiple levels, ensuring detailed insight into the operational aspects of the system.

Figure 6: Logic representation of the CAM.

3.1.3 Using CAM to Deploy and Monitor Applications

CAM has been developed in a customizable way, which allows user DEV to customise, deploy, and enhance its functionality within a K8s environment, considering different applications. Steps to adapt CAM to a new application are defined next.

3.1.3.1 Deployment

First, user DEV must have a running K8s cluster; afterwards, user DEV MUST define the application to deploy across Edge-Cloud via the CAM YAML file²².

The application can then be deployed with the following command:

```
kubectl apply -f <your yaml file name>
```

Example:

```
kubectl apply -f codecoappinstance3.yaml
```

3.1.3.2 Monitoring and Managing

To monitor the status of the deployed application instance run:

```
kubectl get codecoapp <your application name> -n he-codeco-acm
```

²² Currently, CAM is defined based on the usual K8s CLI approach. However, the aim in CODECO is to provide the user with a Web-based dashboard which facilitates the definition of the application and its requirements.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Example:

```
kubectl get codecoapp codecoappinstance3 -n he-codeco-acm
```

Check logs and metrics to ensure the application is running smoothly and meeting the specified resource limits and performance metrics.

3.1.3.3 Modifying an Application

- **Customizing Services:**
 - Add more services to the [spec.codecoapp-msspec](#) array to expand the application’s functionality.
 - Customize container images, resource limits, and ports to meet your specific requirements.
- **Enhancing Network and Resource Specifications:**
- Modify the *nwbandwidth* and *nwlatency* parameters of [spec.codecoapp-msspec](#) to optimize network performance based on your application needs.
 - Adjust resource allocations such as CPU and memory in the *podspec.containers.resources.limits*²³ section of the service to better align with the workload demands.
- **Compliance, QoS, and Security:**
 - Modify *complianceClass*, *qosClass*, and *securityClass* to align with your organisation's standards and policies.

After modifying the CAM yaml file, apply it to the system as described in subsection 4.1.1.

3.1.3.4 Adding Custom Metrics and Status Indicators

User DEV can add more metrics (and respective mechanisms) to monitor the CODECO metrics via Prometheus. This is useful, for instance, in the case of application metrics that were not defined in CODECO, but that may be required in a specific use-case not being addressed by CODECO.

3.1.4 Sub-components’ Specification, Implementation and Integration

3.1.4.1 Code Structure

The [ACM component, available via the CODECO ECL GitLab](#), has the structure described in Table 5.

Table 5: CODECO ACM code structure.

File	Function
UML-Diagrams/ ApplicationModel_Update.svg	Unified Modelling Language (UML) diagram of the application model
prom_rules	Directory containing Prometheus rules YAML files
prom_rules/example.rules.yaml	An example Prometheus rule file
scripts/post_deploy.sh	Shell script that is executed after ACM deployment
scripts/pre_deploy.sh	Shell script that is executed before the ACM deployment
controllers/ codecoapp_controller.go	Contains logic for reconciling CODECO CR

²³ <https://k8s.io/docs/concepts/configuration/manage-resources-containers/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

File	Function
config/cluster/kind-config.yaml	Configuration file used to define the setup and properties of K8s cluster created with kind
config/samples/codeco_v1alpha1_codecoapp_ver3.yaml	Sample CODECO CR YAML file
config/crd/bases/codeco.he-codeco.eu_codecoapps.yaml	CODECO CR definition
Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce ACM operator image
Makefile	Makefile containing build, deployment and other commands for the operator

3.1.4.2 Pre-Requisites

In terms of hardware or software, ACM will require a lab environment with at least a cluster installed, e.g., a K8s-based cluster. This cluster needs to be dimensioned to have enough resources to accommodate the ACM component installation, which will also include the whole CODECO platform with all its sub-components. There are no additional software or hardware necessary if not those already specified for CODECO, since ACM is the main integration point to enable the CODECO platform and its features.

3.1.4.3 Installation Guide

ACM is the integration point towards the user, it is also in charge of the system installation - the user can install the whole CODECO framework by installing the CODECO meta-operator (which is part of ACM), where this process triggers the installation of the entire CODECO system on the cluster to be managed and configured. There are two common user scenarios, application deployment (user DEV) and K8s infrastructure (platform) configuration (user MGT). For example, user MGT can deploy (or configure) the CODECO platform.

Currently the installation is CLI-based only, and it supports installing all the components in one command. In the future we plan to use the operator hub model (a kind of app store for operators) which enables one operator to install multiple components according to the dependencies and provides a Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the installation.

The installation steps are described in the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab, [ACM readme](#), and are summarized as follows considering KinD as basis for deployment. It should be highlighted that CODECO can be tested with any other K8s tool, and KinD is here referenced to assist the reader in experimenting with the code.

Get the ACM code:

```
git clone https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm
```

Create a (KinD) cluster:

Change to the ACM directory and run:

```
kind create cluster --config ./config/cluster/kind-config.yaml
```

Build and deploy ACM

Scripts are used to automate the installation of the entire CODECO platform. The only steps that the user DEV needs to follow to install the platform are listed next:

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- First, you will need a connection to an image registry established in docker or podman. This is done by issuing the docker login command²⁴. It is recommended to use a secure login²⁵. This procedure may change based on the repository selected.

Then, a container image of the operator should be built and pushed into an image registry (such as docker hub, quay.io and others). This can be done using the following command:

```
make docker-build docker-push IMG=<some-registry>/<image-name>:<tag>
```

Example:

```
make docker-build docker-push IMG=hecodeco/codecoapp-  
operator:latest
```

Then deploy ACM on the cluster using the command below:

```
make deploy IMG=<some-registry>/<image-name>:<tag>
```

Example:

```
make deploy IMG=hecodeco/codecoapp-operator:latest
```

This automatically installs the other CODECO components (SWM, NetMA, MDM, PDLC), their corresponding dependencies, and the Prometheus operator on the same cluster.

3.1.4.4 Inputs & Outputs

ACM gets as input:

- The application description CR – and instance of the spec from the CAM CRD.
- A description of the cluster topology (the file kind-config.yaml) - in the next phase this information will be gathered directly from OCM.

ACM has as output:

- Coarse grained metrics and status description of the application in the status part of the CAM CRD (updated once a minute).
- The deployment topology (the nodes used by the application, and the pods that are deployed on each node) - this is also part of the status field in the CAM CRD.

The ACM exposed APIs (the CODECO APIs) are declarative APIs following the K8s methodology. The CAM described above is used both for input and for output of the application APIs – for the input it represents the desired state of the application, and as output it includes application deployment information and coarse-grained information about the resource usage (for example, average CPU usage, memory usage and energy consumption in a specific time window), and application behavior (for example, observed QoS).

3.1.5 ACM Code Open Issues

Table 6 provides a list of code open issues for ACM, which are expected to be handled in the next release (M24).

Table 6: ACM code open issues.

²⁴ <https://docs.docker.com/reference/cli/docker/login/>

²⁵ <https://docs.docker.com/security/for-developers/access-tokens/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

ID	Description
ACM-OI-1	Developer dashboard for user interaction with CAM.
ACM-OI-2	Integration with NetMA (Nemesys)
ACM-OI-3	Integration of the NetMA network performance metrics in the CAM status.

3.2 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness

3.2.1 Component Description

PDLC is at the heart of CODECO orchestration. Based on the infrastructure data collected by ACM (via Prometheus), NetMA and MDM, PDLC has two functions. First, it provides data-computing-network node costs (**aggregated node costs**) based on specific target performance profiles selected by the user (e.g., optimizing the overall infrastructure for resilience). This implies that the notion of a node in the infrastructure embodies network, data, and computing-awareness. Second, it provides an estimate of overall system stability based on privacy-preserving de centralised learning approaches. PDLC is currently envisioned to run on both master and worker nodes of K8s.

To be able to achieve this purpose, PDLC integrates, as the name points out, 3 sub-modules: **data processing**; **cross-layer metadata aggregation** (context-awareness); **decentralised learning**, as illustrated in Figure 7:

- **Data Preprocessing (PDLC-DP):** the subcomponent that acts as an input interface of PDLC with all other CODECO components. Responsible for obtaining all necessary data and performing the needed pre-processing operations (cleaning, normalization, etc.) for the data to be ready for use by the other subcomponents.
- **Context-Awareness (PDLC-CA):** the subcomponent responsible for generating node costs that relate with target performance profiles selected by the user, such as greenness or resilience.
- **Decentralised Learning (PDLC-DL):** the subcomponent responsible for exploiting the context information provided by PDLC-CA through privacy-aware de centralised learning algorithm to add an additional intelligence layer to the operations of CODECO. It currently contains two models, a Graph Neural Network (GNN) and a Reinforcement Learning agent (RL). Furthermore, this sub-component will include Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) pipelines to orchestrate the (re)training process of the mentioned models.

Figure 7 depicts the architecture of the different PDLC sub-components and their interactions with other CODECO components, namely ACM, MDM, NetMA and SWM. On the other hand, PDLC interfaces to other components are shown in Table 7, where the status of the implementation in the current release of the CODECO open-source Toolkit is detailed as well. The entire source code of all subcomponents of PDLC is available in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab, under [PDLC](#). In the following subsections, implementation details about each of the subcomponents along with relevant links to specific repositories, readme files, configuration files, etc. will be provided.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 7: PDLC sub-components and interfaces [2].

Table 7: Status of PDLC interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-PDLC-ACM-1	Obtaining data collected by other CODECO components and made available via CRs of those components.	CRs	Input
I-MDM-PDLC-1	Data collected by CODECO MDM	CR	Input
I-PDLC-SWM-1	Adding new attributes to SWM application CRs related to performance profiles generated by PDLC-CA	CR	Output
I-PDLC-SWM-2	Adding new attributes to SWM CRs related to node recommendations for application workload placement generated by PDLC-RL	CR	Output
I-SWM-PDLC-1	PDLC will be able to know about scheduling/placement decisions of SWM by accessing the <i>AssignmentPlan</i> CR	CR	Input
I-NET-PDLC-2	PDLC receives underlay and overlay network metrics from NetMA	CR	Input

3.2.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation, and Integration

Figure 8 depicts the main interactions between the PDLC subcomponents as well as their input and output to other CODECO components.

Figure 8: Main interactions between the PDLC sub-components.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.2.2.1 PDLC-DP

PDLC-DP's major objective is to deliver high-quality, interpretable data, continuously collected from ACM, MDM, and NetMA CRDs, using techniques like cleaning, integration, transformation, and normalization. This data is then provided to other PDLC sub-components, PDLC-CA, and PDLC-DL, for further processing. The PDLC-DP architecture includes two main modules, a **gatherer** responsible for collecting the data from other PDLC components and a **pre-processing module** responsible for transforming the collected data.

3.2.2.1.1 Implementation details

The **gatherer** module is responsible for gathering all the metrics in the form of CR values provided by the other CODECO components, saving them in memory for PDLC-DP to use and then destroying²⁶. Another responsibility of the Gatherer is the continuous validation and recreation of the cluster topology from the topological information provided by NetMA.

The cluster topology is described by the Gatherer in an adjacency matrix for the rest of the PDLC subcomponents to use. This procedure is happening in a configurable amount of time in order to easily fit with PDLC needs. Figure 9 shows the internal functionalities of the Gatherer module using a UML activity diagram.

The Gatherer module takes a multi-threading approach in the collection of the CODECO CRD values. On its startup, it initializes three queues for each of the three other PDLC subcomponents. Then it starts a new thread for each of the preprocessing procedures for PDLC-CA, PDLC-GNNs and PDLC-RL. The activities of these threads are shown in the right hand-side of Figure 9. After the initial startup of the threads and the initialization of the queues, the Gatherer collects the CR values from the other CODECO components and integrates them into an internal data structure called Cluster Sample Object, with the schema depicted in Figure 10 and the detailed description of the CODECO metrics (rf. to D10) that are currently implemented in v2.0 are summarized in Table 8.

Figure 9: PDLC-DP Gatherer module internal functionality.

²⁶ Currently, CODECO metrics status is managed via a transient approach. However, over time and based on the needs of PDLC, this situation may adapt to consider long-term state.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

When a CA, GNN or RL Thread is started by the Gatherer, it collects all the Cluster Sample in its corresponding queue and then calls the pre-processing module (PP) to execute the corresponding tasks. Once PP module ends, the corresponding thread sleeps for a configurable amount of time, before calling itself again to create a continuous pre-processing procedure by the PDLC-DP-PP functionalities.

Figure 10: PDLC-DP Gatherer module's Cluster Sample Schema.

The **data pre-processing** module is responsible for cleaning, curating, and preparing the data provided by the Gatherer. This module encompasses various operations, including data validation, transformation, normalization, integrity checks, and quality assurance processes.

The preprocessing module executes various processing operations tailored to each PDLC sub-component. However, these operations are performed concurrently to minimize execution time, as illustrated in Figure 11. When the processing operations are completed, the processed data are stored in different CSV files - each one to serve the subcomponents functionalities and declares again its availability to the Gatherer in order to start receiving new data. The preprocessing operations designed to support each PDLC subcomponent are described in Table 9.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 11: PDLC-DP preprocessing module subcomponent internal functionality.

Table 8: PDLC-DP preprocessing operations for each of the PDLC subcomponents.

Sub-component	Required Metrics	Update Interval	Normalization	Additional Information
PDLC-CA	Metrics for all cluster nodes collected from CODECO-ACM, CODECO-MDM, and CODECO-NetMA via CRDs	1 minute	Min-Max Normalization Fixed values used for consistent data-scale schema	Output stored in a tailored persistent volume exclusively for CODECO-PDLC
PDLC-GNN	Normalized values for: Node CPU, Node Memory, Node bandwidth (ingress and egress)	1 minute	Min-Max Normalization Dynamic normalization procedure replacing previous min and max values if new values are lower/higher	Continuously updated as new observations are collected and processed
PDLC-RL	Specific metrics detailing node CPU and memory usage	1 minute	Normalization is not required	New min and max values documented alongside observations to facilitate denormalization by PDLC-GNN

3.2.2.1.2 Code Structure

Table 9 provides a description of the CODECO PDLC-DP main source files.

Table 9: Description of the main PDLC-DP source code files.

File	Function
apply-component.sh	Installs PDLC-DP in the cluster
delete-component.sh	Removes PDLC-DP from the cluster
src/k8s_calling/sample.py	This script is used to generate fake CRs from CRDs in order to be tested from the PDLC-DP. Additionally, grabs the sample topology from the NetMA CR and stores it in the defined persistent volume used by all the PDLC subcomponents.
src/models	Includes all the pre-trained models for both the GNNs and RL. For the RL models, examples are provided illustrating how the records are represented in the CRD utilized by SWM. These models are copied directly to the defined persistent volume used by the PDLC subcomponents.
src/gatherer.py	The gathering module. It is responsible for gathering the CRs from CRDs. Once the dataflow is initialized the gatherer creates queues for providing the data to the preprocessing module using threads, each one for each PDLC subcomponent.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

File	Function
src/pp_module/ca.py	This script is responsible for executing all the preprocessing operations concerning the PDLC-CA subcomponent. It is located in the folder named `pp_module`, which is part of the preprocessing module.
src/pp_module/gnn.py	This script is responsible for executing all the preprocessing operations required for the GNNs as part of the PDLC-DL subcomponent. It is located in the folder named `pp_module`, which is part of the preprocessing module.
src/pp_module/rl.py	This script is responsible for executing all the preprocessing operations required for the RL as part of the PDLC-DL subcomponent. It is located in the folder named `pp_module`, which is part of the preprocessing module.
src/pp_module/features_dict.py	This script serves as a guide for correcting the labelling of cross-layer metrics and functions as a support tool. It is located in the folder named `pp_module`, which is part of the preprocessing module.
src/pp_module/utilities.py	This script, located in the pp_module folder as part of the preprocessing module, provides support functions for the key functions (CA, RL, GNNs). It is located in the folder named `pp_module`, which is part of the preprocessing module.
src/data_examples/	This directory includes examples of the PDLC-DP input data and examples representing the final output .csv files that PDLC-DP provides to the other PDLC subcomponents (CA, GNNs, RL) - in different sub-directories

3.2.2.1.3 Selected technologies

The PDLC-DP sub-component has been designed and developed entirely by using the Python programming language versions 3.10+ and 3.12+. The respective packages that were used during the component's development are listed below along with their relevant description:

- **K8s**: a Python client for K8s.
- **NumPy** (Numerical Python): an open source, widely used Python library that provides computation functionalities and fast operations on multidimensional array objects, mostly used in the model's data preprocessing code.
- **Pandas** (Python Data Analysis): an open-source Python library that uses DataFrame and Series data structures for efficient and flexible data analysis and manipulation, mostly used in the model's data preprocessing code.
- **Requests**: an open-source library that allows sending sending Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) requests.

3.2.2.1.4 Pre-requisites

- In terms of the infrastructure, a K8s cluster needs to be set up.
- The PDLC-DP Gatherer and Preprocessing module subcomponents are deployed together as a standalone component and are working continuously expecting CRs to be generated by the relevant CRDs.
- In terms of software the [pre-requisites are available via the requirements.txt](#) file in the PDLC-DP repository.

3.2.2.1.5 Installation guide

The complete process for deploying the PDLC-DP component is detailed in the README.md file found in the CODECO ECL GitLab, [PDLC repository](#). This document provides comprehensive instructions for deploying the PDLC-DP component, including the necessary YAML files (deployment, role, role-binding) and bash scripts for automated deployment. Additionally, the entire source code, along with the respective Dockerfile for the creation of the image, is available in the repository. The code is thoroughly commented to facilitate a deep understanding.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.2.2.1.6 Inputs and outputs

The input data for the PDLC-DP currently comprises CR values obtained from the CODECO components, namely ACM, MDM, and NetMA, in addition to the output. These CR values are based on 1-minute observations. The PDLC-DP gatherer module provides these CR values to the data pre-processing module, compiling the cluster's state per minute. This collection of CR values then serves as input for the PDLC-DP pre-processing module, which performs specialized preprocessing operations to create and update the files detailed in Table 10, which are available under [pdlc-dp/src/data_examples](#).

Table 10: PDLC-DP Output to Corresponding subcomponents.

PDLC subcomponent	Final PDLC-DP output
PDLC-CA	data_CA.csv
PDLC-GNN	data_GNN.csv
PDLC-RL	test_nodes.csv test_integracio.csv

3.2.2.1.7 UML sequence diagram

A communication sequence diagram for the PDLC-DP component is provided in Figure 12.

Figure 12: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-DP.

3.2.2.2 PDLC-CA

The current version of PDLC-CA is focused on a single cluster operation. It relies on inputs from other CODECO components (e.g., computational parameters such as CPU, memory; network parameters such as bandwidth, latency, link energy, node degree; data metrics such as data compliance, data size) and from Prometheus. The existing parameters are combined to serve a selected performance profile, such as optimising the infrastructure for greenness or

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

resilience²⁷. The performance profile, which is currently defined statically in the code, will be an attribute of the CAM selected by the user DEV during the deployment of an application.

The reader should check D10 for an explanation on the computational principles and rationale behind the PDLC-CA operation.

Currently, PDLC-CA relies on simple heuristics to rank existing nodes based on the selected target profile and considering a combination of available CODECO metrics. The output of PDLC-CA (node score for the selected target performance profile, e.g., resilience), is made available in the form of a CSV file, which is stored in the PDLC share volume, where the distributed learning subcomponent of PDLC (PDLC-DL) is able to access it to use it as part of the RL states.

3.2.2.2.1 Implementation details

The current version of PDLC-CA has been envisioned to work based on a single cluster scenario, which can be set up with any available tool. The current code provides the possibility to experiment PDLC-CA with minikube or with KinD, with a variable number of nodes, and provides an example for two specific target profiles: **greenness** and **resilience**, providing directions on how a developer can create new heuristics for other potential performance profiles.

The code provided is based on two different branches under [PDLC/PDLC-CA](#):

- [main](#), provides the latest PDLC-CA development in CODECO (CA-integration). This corresponds to an integration of the sub-component with the other PDLC components.
- [CA-Standalone](#), which provides a version of the code that a user can use on a cluster, not connected to other PDLC sub-components, e.g., eventually to assess different schedulers (with some adaptation).

These two versions differ only in the input and output storage. CA-Standalone has as input the CRDs provided by the CODECO Data Generator and as output a CRD file. CA-integration (main) is interconnected to the data processing module via a volume and writes the output to a .csv file which the PDLC-DL module uses as input. Hence, the remainder code and logic remain the same and the explanation next fits the code provided in the two repositories). The user can therefore set different clusters and test PDLC-CA in standalone mode; and then use the generated output (CRD and csv format) to interact with other CODECO components. PDLC-DL can also use the generated CRD as input.

The input from PDLC-CA relates with the CODECO metrics provided by components ACM, NetMA, MDM. PDLC gets these metrics and processes (as well as normalizes) them via the PDLC-DP. Then, PDLC-CA gets as input the normalized CODECO metrics, and computes a node cost for specific target profiles, such as resilience, greenness.

The code has been developed so that other target profiles can be easily created. It is currently possible to test two specific target profiles, which are provided as potential examples on how aggregated node costs based on a performance profile can be implemented.

Greenness Profile (g(n)), focuses on helping to create an infrastructure with the lowest possible energy consumption.

²⁷ In CODECO, these are currently the target profiles being implemented. However, in future versions of PDLC-CA different aggregated costs for other types of target profile, e.g., QoE, will be explored.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- **Purpose:** to select nodes that can contribute to achieve an infrastructure (for an application group) that has the least energy expenditure possible.
- **Rationale:** the lower the node energy expenditure; the lower the sum of energy consumed in links (transmission); the lower the node greenness cost is.
- **Example:** $g(n)=node_energy(n) \times ulink_energy(n)$, where $node_energy(n)$ is a parameter provided via ACM/Prometheus and corresponds to the energy spent on node n over a specific time period; and $ulink_energy(n)$ corresponds to the total energy expenditure due to link transmissions on links that have the node as a source.

Resilience Profile $r(n)$, is focused on the selection of nodes that will maximise the resilience of the infrastructure.

- **Purpose:** Nodes are weighted for their contribution to resilience of the selected infrastructure
- **Rationale:** the higher the number of link failures associated with the node; the smaller the $node_degree$; the lower is the resilience of the node
- **Example:** $r(n)=node_failure(n) * 1/node_degree(n) * node_net_failure(n)$, Where $node_failure(n)$ is the average failures over a time window (EMA), $node_degree(n)$ is the number of active neighbor nodes and $node_net_failure(n)$ is Sum of failures of all links of a node.

The parameters are provided by NetMA ($node_net_failure$, $node_degree$) and ACM ($node_failure$).

3.2.2.2.2 Code structure

The files that compose PDLC-CA are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Summary of main PDLC-CA source code files.

File	Function
apply_controllers.sh	Installs PDLC-CA in the cluster
delete_controller.sh	Removes PDLC-CA from the cluster
Extractor.py	Data extractor, it fetches the normalized metrics from the data_CA.csv file stored in the PDLC shared volume and makes the metrics available as a return of the function <code>get_metrics()</code> .
Cost_estimator.py	It has as input the CAM performance_profile (currently statically defined), and the normalized metrics from the <code>get_metrics</code> function from the <code>Extractor.py</code> script. It generates as output an aggregated value for that profile, for each node, based on CODECO NetMA, MDM, ACM parameters being monitored. The output is stored as a <code>metrics.csv</code> file.
ca.csv	Output of PDLC-CA, generated by <code>crd_data_extraction.py</code>
ca_controller/	PDLC-CA controller and respective <code>yaml</code> files.
crd_data_extraction/ca_crd_extractor.py	Creates the output in a <code>csv</code> format, by reading the CA CRD.

3.2.2.2.3 Selected Technologies

PDLC-CA has been implemented in Python v3.0. Input and output are based on YAML (CRD).

3.2.2.2.4 Pre-requisites

Rf. to the [README of the](#) PDLC-CA code for a detailed list of requirements:

- A cluster needs to be set up. For the current code there is a how-to that can be used with KinD or minikube, for testing purposes.
- The CODECO framework or CODECO data generator needs to be installed and run on the cluster to generate a **data.csv** (input) with the correct format.
- Software requirements are listed in [requirements.txt](#).

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.2.2.2.5 Installation Guide

A [detailed installation guide is available with the code of PDLC-CA \(readme\)](#).

1. Get the PDLC-CA code:

```
git clone git@gitlab.eclipse.org:eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca.git
```

2. Set up a K8s cluster:

In this release, examples on how to set a cluster are described for KinD or minikube.

With KinD:

1. Create kind config file:

```
cat > kind-config.yaml <<EOF
# three node (two workers) cluster config
kind: Cluster
apiVersion: kind.x-k8s.io/v1alpha4
nodes:
- role: control-plane
- role: worker
- role: worker
EOF
```

2. Create cluster:

```
kind create cluster --name <cluster_name> --config kind-config.yaml
```

With minikube:

Set up a cluster with 1 node (control-plane):

```
minikube start
```

(or) Set up a cluster with x nodes:

```
minikube start --nodes x -p <cluster-name>
```

3. Get data from your cluster

PDLC-CA will use data collected by the CODECO components NetMA (network metrics); MDM (data workflow metrics); ACM (application and user metrics), by i) getting the metrics directly from the CODECO framework installation; ii) running the [CODECO synthetic data generator](#) (Experimentation Framework and Demonstrations/Data Generators and Datasets/Synthetic Data Generator) on your cluster to be able to retrieve metrics that is used as inputs to the PDLC-CA component.

After installing PDLC-CA as part of the CODECO framework, you can view the output CSV file that contains the performance profile costs for nodes within the cluster by performing the following commands:

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

4. Get the pod name

Use the kubectl get pods command to retrieve the name of the PDLC-CA pod

```
POD_NAME=$(kubectl get pods -n he-codeco-pdlc -l app=pdlc-ca -o jsonpath="{.items[0].metadata.name}")
```

5. Execute the command within the pod

Use the kubectl exec command to execute a shell command inside the retrieved pod. This command changes the directory to /data/RL and displays the contents of metrics.csv.

```
pip3 install -r requirements_e.txt
python3 ca_crd_extractor.py
```

```
kubectl exec -it $POD_NAME -- sh -c "cd /data/RL && cat metrics.csv"
```

```
chmod -R 777.
```

```
./apply-controller.sh
```

3.2.2.2.6 Inputs and outputs

- **Input of PDLC-CA corresponds to CSV file provided by PDLC-DL.** PDLC-CA fetches the input metrics from the path [/data/CA/data_CA.csv](#) stored at the PDLC component shared volume.
- **Output of PDLC-CA** is provided in CSV format and stored in the PDLC shared volume in the following path [/data/RL/metrics.csv](#).

3.2.2.2.7 UML Sequence Diagram

The communication sequence for PDLC-CA is provided in Figure 13.

Figure 13: UML Sequence diagram of PDLC-CA.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.2.2.3 PDLC-DL – GNNs

The PDLC-DL *Spatio Temporal Graph Neural Network (STGNN)* subcomponent is responsible for producing node resource usage predictions (CPU and memory) and providing them as input for the PDLC *Reinforcement Learning* model (PDLC-RL). The code can be found in the CODECO GitLab under [PDLC/PDLC-DL/PDLC-GNNs](#).

3.2.2.3.1 Implementation details

The GNN models can currently provide predictions for the CPU and memory usage of a cluster's nodes. Every 1 minute, the subcomponent reads the new values of CPU and memory usage per each node, which the PDLC-DP subcomponent gathers and normalizes. It uses the latest historical observations, as well as the cluster topology, so that it can consider both the spatial and temporal dependencies of the nodes and provide predictions for the next 5, 15 and 30 minutes. These forecasts are given as input to PDLC-RL. The key purpose of this approach is therefore to provide a forecasting on the usage of the infrastructure, to further assist the workload placement. At the current stage of development, the code developed simply considers the computational aspects, expecting to be extended in a near future.

The workflow that is associated with the GNN models is handled, as illustrated in Figure 14, by a controller, which includes the GNN orchestrator and the Inference service. The GNN orchestrator is responsible for continuously reading data that are written to a .csv file by the PDLC-DP subcomponent. Every one minute it reads the normalized CPU and memory usage of all nodes of the cluster. It then creates the appropriate request body and sends an API request to the Inference service every minute. The Inference service continuously reads the given cluster topology and when an inference request is received, it selects the appropriate pretrained model based on the number of nodes, the requested metric (CPU or memory) and the requested forecast horizon (5, 15 or 30 minutes). The output of the Inference service is written in three .csv files, which contain forecasts for the next 5, 15 and 30 minutes, respectively. Those files are saved in the PDLC shared volume to be accessed by the RL model.

Figure 14: Internal architecture of the PDLC-GNN sub-component.

The pre-trained models of this subcomponent are dependent on the number of nodes. Therefore, for the CODECO Basic Toolkit, the existing pre-trained models correspond to 2 and 3 node cluster topologies. However, the code for training new models and saving pre-trained models to be used for inference can be found under [PDLC-GNNs/STGNN_training](#).

This training currently has to be performed offline and is not part of the integrated CODECO framework. Detailed instructions on pre-requisites and running the code to create new pretrained models can be found in the respective [README](#) file.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.2.2.3.2 Code Structure

The PDLC-GNN sub-component main source code files are briefly summarized in Table 12.

Table 12: Description of the main PDLC-GNN source code files.

File	Function
Inference	
stggn_controller.py	Module that reads new data every minute, formats the historical values into the Javascript Object Notation (JSON) body and makes a request to the Inference API.
app.py	Code that implements the Inference Service API, selects the appropriate models based on the number of nodes in the topology, makes the predictions and writes the forecasted values in the appropriate files.
inference.py	Function that uses model architecture from model.py , loads weights of pretrained models and performs prediction using prediction.py
model.py	Code including the STGNN model architecture and required classes
prediction.py	File where model predictions are generated and predictions are denormalized, to provide the denormalized values in the output files
load_data.py	File that reads data from the Inference API request body and performs the appropriate formatting of the data to be used in the inference function
data_formatting.py	Code including functions for formatting data into tensorflow dataset and for parsing cluster topology
Training	
main.py	Code that is used to trigger model training, based on input arguments.
training.py	Code including the STGNN model architecture and required classes

3.2.2.3.3 Selected Technologies

- **NumPy** (Numerical Python): an open source, widely used Python library that provides computation functionalities and fast operations on multidimensional array objects, mostly used in the model's data preprocessing code.
- **Pandas** (Python Data Analysis): an open-source Python library that uses DataFrame and Series data structures for efficient and flexible data analysis and manipulation, mostly used in the model's data preprocessing code.
- **TensorFlow**: an open-source framework that provides tools and libraries for the development of machine learning models, used in the model's architecture.
- **Requests**: an open-source library that allows sending HTTP requests.
- **Flask**: an open-source lightweight web application framework.
- **K8s**: a Python client for K8s.

3.2.2.3.4 Pre-requisites

- A K8s cluster needs to be set up.
- In terms of data the PDLC-DP component is required and the input data, as well as the cluster topology file must be in the PDLC shared volume.
- The folder of the pre-trained models must be in the PDLC shared volume.
- Software requirements are available in requirements.txt for inference and the orchestrator.

3.2.2.3.5 Installation guide

Detailed instructions on how to deploy and run the controller and inference modules of the GNNs subcomponent can be found in the [PDLC-GNNs README](#) file. The deployment files of the Inference service and the controller can be found in the following links:

- Inference deployment file: [Inference deployment file link](#)
- Controller deployment file: [Controller deployment file link](#)

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

The Inference Deployment file includes Deployment and a Service specification. In the environment variables of the inference deployment file, the parameters that need to be specified are the namespace where the service is deployed, the path where the pretrained models are stored, as well as the path where the forecasts' files should be saved. Once the file is applied, a pod as along with a deployment and a service are created in the K8s cluster.

The Docker image of the GNN inference module is available via the CODECO DockerHub repository: [hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-inference:2.0.0](https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-inference:2.0.0).

The deployment file of the controller includes a Deployment specification and the environment variables that need to be specified are the GNN_PATH, which indicates the path of the input data file and the NAMESPACE, which corresponds to the namespace, where the inference service is deployed. Once the file is applied, a pod and a deployment are created in the K8s cluster.

The Docker image of the controller module is available under the CODECO Docker Hub: [hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-controller:2.0.0](https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-controller:2.0.0).

3.2.2.3.6 Inputs and Outputs

The input data of the GNN inference service given by the PDLC-DP component is written in the "[data_GNN.csv](#)" file and include the timestamp of the given values, the names of each node, the normalized CPU and memory values, as well as the minimum and maximum values with which the normalized values were calculated for both CPU and memory.

The output data of the GNN inference service consists of three separate files available under [outputs](#): "[forecasts5.csv](#)", "[forecasts15.csv](#)" and "[forecasts30.csv](#)" for the corresponding forecast horizons of 5, 15 and 30 minutes. The files include the timestamp which corresponds to the predicted values, the name of each node and the denormalized CPU and memory predicted values.

3.2.2.3.7 UML Sequence Diagram

Figure 15 provides the communication sequence of PDLC-GNN, providing a perspective on its overall operation in PDLC.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 15: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-GNN.

3.2.2.4 PDLC-DL – RL

The PDLC-DL subcomponent provides node placement recommendations for new and running pods in a K8s cluster based on the chosen performance profile. This is done by enhancing the capabilities of the scheduler used in CODECO by using *Proximal Policy Optimization* (PPO) algorithms, and a DRL agent.

3.2.2.4.1 Implementation Details

The implementation of the subcomponent is done by the creation of a controller that operates all the capabilities of the sub-component. This controller selects the desired model depending on the number of nodes and the performance profile chosen and performs an infinite loop where it pools for new data incoming from PDLC sub-components. This is done by reading a series of csv files that are provided by all subcomponents of PDLC in order to boost the overall capabilities of the component.

Firstly, from PDLC-DP PDLC-RL obtains the current state of the system (currently, CPU and RAM available) and the information about pods (new and running ones). This is the basis for the functioning of RL, as the current state of the system and the resources of pods are needed in order to generate recommendations.

Secondly, from PDLC-GNNs, PDLC-RL checks for new predictions (if available, after 5, 15, and 30 minutes as detailed in section 3.2.2.3) and uses this data as the input of the network instead of the state obtained from DP (CPU and memory for all nodes). This provides PDLC-RL with improved capabilities to give the best possible recommendations at long term, as node recommendations are done with forecasts of the consumed values instead of the real ones. Given the nature of clusters and the average time for pod creation, this improves the overall

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

performance of the system. Finally, from PDLC-CA, the aggregated node costs (e.g., resilience node cost, greenness node cost) are obtained and later used as input for PDLC-RL to provide recommendations.

Once the pooling phase is done, the PDLC-RL algorithm performs inference for new pods and writes them in the SWM CRs that are used in SWM to start a deployment as soon as new pods are received. For already running pods, a configurable parameter controls how often pods are revisited (to generate new possible recommendations). Inside the reallocation logic, a comparison is performed between the new confidence values and the old ones: if the *Mean Squared Error (MSE)* comparing these two lists is bigger than 0.5 and the node with more confidence is different, the new confidence values are written in SWM CRs. Additionally, the assignment plan from SWM is periodically obtained in order to use it in future iterations of CODECO as feedback for the learning algorithm.

Because of a dependency on the number of nodes in the models, in this version of the CODECO Toolkit, PDLC-RL is only compatible with cluster topologies of 3 to 6 nodes to optimize the greenness profile generated by PDLC-CA.

3.2.2.4.1.1 Model Training

Model Training is currently performed outside CODECO, in an emulator to speed up the training process of the models. This emulator has been developed and tested at I2CAT and emulates the functioning of CODECO and its components (up to the greenness scenario). The model training module contains several scripts and components can be used independently or together as a single component in two different modes: training or inference testing. Instructions of use can be found in the [PDLC-RL/Training/Readme](#) file.

3.2.2.4.2 Code Structure

A summarized description of the main PDLC-RL source files is provided in Table 13 Table 13.

Table 13: Description of the main PDLC-RL source code files.

File	Function
Integration D12	
Inference_controller.py	Main file of RL component, it controls the behaviour of the model in inference mode, where a while True logic loops through all the functionalities previously explained. Auxiliar functions and model are declared in same file.
Training	
main.py	Main file of the RL Training, it controls the behaviour of the model in training mode, it also includes a short inference mode to test trained models.
codeco_env.py	Gymnasium environment emulating a K8s cluster functioning, used to train and emulate RL agents.
data_preprocess.py	Functions used to ensure that the format of the data used by the training and testing mode of this branch of code is correct.
k8node_config.py	Class that emulates a K8s Node, used by the codeco_env class in order to emulate the K8s cluster, just an auxiliar class.
training_controller.py	Orchestrator of training and validation processes regarding RL agents used in CODECO.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.2.2.4.3 Selected Technologies

- **Numpy** (Numerical Python): A fundamental package for scientific computing in Python, providing support for arrays, matrices, and various mathematical functions.
- **K8s**: python library to access the K8s API, used to access and modify CRDs from PDLC-DL-RL.
- **PyTorch**: An open-source Deep Learning (DL) framework based on the Torch library. Used to create, train, and manage neural networks in commercial and research applications.
- **OpenAI Gym**²⁸: An open-source toolkit developed by OpenAI and maintained by the Faram foundation, which provides the tools to develop environments in which RL methods can be latter trained.
- **Stable Baselines**³: A set of reliable implementations of reinforcement learning algorithms in Python, built on top of PyTorch and OpenAI Gym, used in training as inference mode provides a custom solution to save space in images.

3.2.2.4.4 Pre-requisites

This version of PDLC-RL is dependent on the other CODECO components. All other subcomponents of PDLC are required by the model to provide recommendations. In particular:

- Cluster setup with CODECO installed in it, with all the components of PDLC in the same node.
- PDLC-DP and CA MUST be used for input data.
- PDLC-GNNs are optional but highly recommended. If not present, monitoring data will be used as input instead of the forecasting values generated by GNNs.
- SWM is needed if a scheduler is required. Otherwise, the output CRs must be provided for the standalone installation as explained in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**
- The number of nodes of the cluster must be between three and six.
- Software requirements are specified in the [requirements.txt](#) file in the code repository.

Additionally, the component has been developed using **Python version 3.10**, requiring the following libraries:

- iteration-utilities == 0.12.1
- Pyyaml == 6.0.1
- Numpy == 2.0.0
- K8s == 30.1.0
- Pytorch-cpu ==2.3.1+cpu

3.2.2.4.5 Installation Guide

Deployment of PDLC-DL-RL subcomponent can be done in two separate ways:

- The subcomponent can be deployed inside of PDLC with the configuration files found in the [PDLC Deployment Repository](#). This is the recommended way to deploy the subcomponent due to the high number of dependencies it has on other CODECO components.
- Additionally, [a standalone deployment](#) can be performed. To deploy the component in this way the user must provide the input dependencies in the form of CSV files and the

²⁸ <https://github.com/openai/gym>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

output CRs to write the generated node recommendations. Extensive documentation on usage of the standalone component can be found in the [README](#) file in the repository.

Additionally, this subcomponent is highly customizable and contains a list of environmental variables that can be changed in K8s:

- **NODE_NUMBER**: Variable that specifies the number of nodes in the cluster, depending on the value a different model will be chosen by the internal logic of the component and different output will be obtained (Number of actions will change depending on this number), default value is 5 and a list of possible values is listed later.
- **CSV_DIR, DP_CSV_NODES, DP_CSV_PODS, CA_CSV, GNNS_X**: Variables that control paths where the component searches for data; CSV_DIR specifies the base path and the rest of the variables specify the location of all the different inputs of the component.
- **REALLOCATION_INTERVAL**: variable that specifies the interval of minutes between pod_reallocations, which is the action of trying to find new allocations for already running pods.

3.2.2.4.6 Inputs and Outputs

Input data for PDLC-RL is obtained via csv files created by the rest of subcomponents in PDLC, namely, DP, CA and GNNs. Additionally, input from SWM is obtained (assignment plans) by reading CRDs. The model also provides output to SWM by writing in CRs, which becomes knowledge for the scheduler solver which decides pod allocation. An overview of the operations (read and write) is presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Inputs and outputs of PDLC-RL.

Kind	Component	File name	Usage
Input	PDLC-DP	test_nodes.csv & test_integracio.csv	Read state of nodes in cluster and pods.
Input	PDLC-CA	ca_metrics.csv	Read Performance profile metrics.
Input	PDLC-GNNs	forecast5.csv	Read state of the system forecast for usage in RL.
Input	SWM	Assignment plan (file in SWM repository)	Assignment plan generated by SWM that will be used in the future as feedback.
Output	SWM	App_CR (file in SWM repository)	Application CR where node_recommendations are written to be latter used by SWM solver.

The SWM CRs are populated with a field called **node_recommendations**, where $\langle key, value \rangle$ pairs representing node and confidence are filled in.

3.2.2.4.7 UML Sequence Diagram

The sequence diagram for PDLC-RL is provided in Figure 16.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 16: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-RL.

3.2.2.5 PDLC-DL - MLOps

The [PDLC-DL-MLOps](#) subcomponent of PDLC-DL is responsible for the retraining of the PDLC-DL GNN models. Currently, this MLOps pipeline is only implemented for the PDLC-GNN model and does not consider the PDLC-RL model.

Furthermore, it can only be used as a standalone component and is not integrated within the wider CODECO framework.

These shortcomings remain as open issues in the implementation of PDLC that will be addressed in the second half of the project.

3.2.2.5.1 Implementation Details

The MLOps subcomponent of PDLC-DL, illustrated in Figure 17, is responsible for the retraining of the PDLC-DL GNN models. Within the GNN controller, a retraining module is responsible for continuously calculating the *Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)*, to evaluate the models' performance and potentially trigger a retraining procedure depending on whether the MAPE is higher than a given threshold. If retraining is necessary, the retraining module of the controller uses the *Kubeflow Pipelines (KFP) Software Development Kit (SDK)* to create a Pipeline Run in Kubeflow. This pipeline performs hyperparameter tuning and trains a new model with the optimal hyperparameters that were identified. After training, the new model is written in the shared volume, overwriting the previous one and in that way the inference service automatically uses the newly trained model.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 17: MLOps pipeline depicting the retraining integration with PDLC-GNN.

The MLOps retraining pipeline consists of three components, as illustrated in Figure 18: one component which performs the data transformation to create the appropriate format for the model’s input, a second component for performing hyperparameter tuning and obtaining the optimal hyperparameters, and a third component for training the new model with the best hyperparameters saving the new model.

← ✓ Run of stgnn-retraining

Figure 18: The workflow operations of the MLOps pipeline for PDLC-GNN.

3.2.2.5.2 Code Structure

The main source code files are summarized in Table 15Table 15.

Table 15: Description of the main PDLC MLOps source code files.

File	Function
data_formatting.py data_formatting.yml	Files that correspond to the data formatting Kubeflow component of the retraining pipeline. The data formatting Kubeflow component is responsible for creating the appropriate format for the models’ input, sampling and splitting the data. In the .yml file the respective image is specified, as well as the input and output parameters for this Kubeflow component.
hyperparameter_tuning.py hyperparameter_tuning.yml	Files that correspond to the hyperparameter tuning Kubeflow component of the retraining pipeline. This Kubeflow component performs a grid search by training the training set with different hyperparameter combinations and evaluates them on a validation set, in order to identify the optimal hyperparameters.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

File	Function
training.py training.yml	Files that correspond to the training Kubeflow component. The optimal hyperparameters of the previous step as taken as input and a new model is trained and evaluated. If the new model outperforms the previous one, it overwrites the previous pretrained model.
run.py	The file which is being run to compile the pipeline and create the retraining pipeline .yaml file. All the inputs, outputs and interdependencies of the factory functions that correspond to the pipeline components are defined in this file.
stggn_retraining.yaml	The file of the compiled retraining pipeline, namely the file of the intermediate representation of the pipeline.
stggn_retraining.py	The code that continuously evaluates the models' performance and triggers the retraining pipeline to run in case of performance degradation.
retraining_pv.yaml	Configuration file for the PersistentVolume that is used by the Kubeflow retraining pipeline and in which the host path is defined.
retraining_pvc.yaml	Configuration file for the PersistentVolumeClaim that corresponds to the PersistentVolume used by the Kubeflow retraining pipeline.
immediate_storage_class.yaml	Configuration file for creating a StorageClass to achieve immediate binding for the PersistentVolume that the Kubeflow retraining pipeline uses. The Immediate mode indicates that volume binding and dynamic provisioning occurs once the PersistentVolumeClaim is created.

3.2.2.5.3 Selected Technologies

The MLOps pipeline and the components for each model instance have been developed using **Python** programming language. The code of the retraining module of the GNN controller, as well as the MLOps pipeline is available under the [Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness - PDLC/PDLC-DL/MLOps](#) repository.

The technologies used are:

- **Docker:** Docker is an open platform for developing and running applications and was used to containerize the code of each component of the MLOps pipeline.
- **Kubeflow:** Kubeflow is an open-source platform for machine learning and MLOps, designed to work with any K8s environment, while providing tools for automating machine learning deployment, scaling, and management. It was utilized to test and run the created MLOps retraining pipeline.

3.2.2.5.4 Pre-requisites

All Pre-requisites applying to the GNN model apply to the MLOps Retraining module. Additionally:

- The GNN inference and GNN controller must be deployed and running.
- A persistent volume and a persistent volume claim must be created in the K8s cluster for the Pod of the training Kubeflow component to be able to save the model in the desired Host Path of the filesystem. The deployment files for the persistent volume and persistent volume claim are provided in the Gitlab repository.
- Kubeflow must be installed and running²⁹.
- For a pipeline to be submitted for execution by the GNN controller retraining module the KFP SDK version 1.8.22 should be used.

3.2.2.5.5 Installation Guide

When the GNNs controller and inference modules are deployed and running, the retraining submodule can also be deployed to continuously evaluate the model performance and trigger the retraining pipeline to run in Kubeflow, to update the models with lower performance with new pretrained models. Detailed instructions on deploying the retraining submodule can be

²⁹ <https://charmed-kubeflow.io/docs/get-started-with-charmed-kubeflow>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

found in the MLOps [README](#) file. Given that Kubeflow is installed, once a retraining is triggered, the retraining pipeline will automatically run in Kubeflow.

3.2.2.5.6 Inputs and Outputs

In order to perform the model evaluation, the retraining module takes as input the new values of the data_GNN.csv file, as well as the corresponding forecasted values of the forecast5.csv, forecast15.csv and forecast30.csv files, to compare the actual and the forecasted values and calculate the MAPE.

Once the retraining Kubeflow pipeline is submitted to run and then completed, if the retraining has yielded a model with lower MAPE than the original one, the output of the pipeline is a new pretrained model and the new files overwrite the substituted model.

3.2.2.5.7 UML Sequence Diagram

The UML sequence diagram for the PDLC-DL MLOps sub-component is illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19: UML sequence diagram of PDLC-MLOps.

3.2.3 PDLC Code Open Issues

Table 16 provides a list of code open issues for PDLC, which are expected to be handled in the next release (M24).

Table 16: PDLC code open Issues.

ID	Description
PDLC-OI-1	Currently, CODECO metrics status is handled via a transient approach. However, over time and based on the needs of PDLC, this situation may adapt to consider long-term state.
PDLC-OI-2	Provide an implementation of PDLC-CA directly feeding a K8s scheduler (implement interface I-PDLC-SWM-1)
PDLC-OI-3	Perform model training within CODECO framework with all CODECO metrics in use (node and link).
PDLC-OI-4	Provide a PDLC implementation where sub-components can reside on different nodes

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

ID	Description
PDLC-OI-5	Create MLOps pipeline for the PDLC-RL model
PDLC-OI-6	Implement pending interfaces between PDLC and other CODECO components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I-PDLC-SWM-1 - I-PDLC-NetMA-1 (optional)
PDLC-OI-7	Update RL and GNNs model designs to remove dependency on number of nodes in the cluster

3.3 NetMA: Network Management and Adaptation

3.3.1 Component Description

NetMA is a network management and adaptation solution that automates the setup of interconnections for flexible Edge-Cloud operations, while addressing the integration of internetworking control and supporting the needs of diverse network environments (fixed, wireless, cellular) that are expected to be managed by CODECO. This CODECO component handles aspects such as network softwarization, secure data exchange, network performance monitoring and integrated network capability exposure through standard-based mechanisms and K8s APIs.

NetMA and its sub-components, along with the main interfaces towards other CODECO components, are represented in **Error! Reference source not found..** It currently considers the following sub-components:

- [Network State Monitoring \(NSM\)](#). This sub-component allows the use of different network probing mechanisms to bring network status to CODECO. Network status is captured at an underlay and overlay perspective, also from an individual link and path perspective. On the current code, two examples of network probing plugins are provided ([netma-nsm-mon](#) and [netma-nsm-npp](#)).
- [Network exposure system \(Nemesys\)](#). Nemesys brings the networking metrics captured by NSM (underlay and overlay) into ACM/Prometheus³⁰ and exposes them in the CODECO system (via ACM) and will also be responsible for the inter-cluster exposure aspects.
- [Secure Connectivity \(L2S-M\)](#). Based on the Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms (L2S-M) solution³¹, secure connectivity in CODECO concerns the secure support of connectivity between pods within a cluster, and for federated clusters. L2S-M is a K8s networking solution that complements the *Container Network Interface (CNI)* plugin approach of K8s to create and manage virtual networks in K8s clusters. In this context, the workloads are configured with an additional network interface (complementary to the one supplied by the CNI of the K8s cluster), and the traffic operated by such interface is handled by SDN, thus ensuring that all data traffic is isolated and enhancing the security in the communication process between micro-services of an application.

³⁰ Currently, NetMA relies on a local Prometheus instantiation to write the metrics. On a next release until M24, NetMA will handle the full integration with the CODECO monitoring architecture (ACM/Prometheus).

³¹ <https://github.com/Networks-it-uc3m/L2S-M>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 20: NetMA and its sub-components.

3.3.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation and Integration

3.3.2.1 NSM: Network State Monitoring

NSM handles the network monitoring aspects, bringing the CODECO networking metrics to the other CODECO components. Currently its design considers different approaches to network probing: monitoring of end-to-end paths; monitoring at a node level; monitoring at a network topology level. The current monitoring subcomponents could be modified or increased as long as the metrics are kept the same, providing more flexibility to NetMA. Examples of metrics being monitored are bandwidth, latency, packet loss, link energy, node degree. For a complete list of metrics collected by NetMA, please check the CODECO architectural design in D10, Annex I [1].

3.3.2.1.1 netma-nsm-npp

3.3.2.1.1.1 Implementation Details

[Netma-nsm-npp](#) is a service in charge of an underlay network probing plugin which considers availability of metrics to meet expected QoS requirements. Currently, it provides throughput, latency, and packet loss based on *Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) Echo Requests*, and *Internet Protocol (IP) sockets*. In the current implementation, probing is set to a periodic approach based on a configurable interval, currently set for 120 seconds by default. The metrics are measured sequentially, one after another, and then, they are exposed by internal Prometheus to the Nemesys subcomponent.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.3.2.1.1.2 Code Structure

The main source code files of [netma-nsm-npp](#) are summarized in Table 17.

Table 17: Description of the main netma-nsm-npp source code files.

File	Function
Dockerfile	Creates a Docker image for the probe.
daemonset.yaml	Configuration file for deploying probing mechanisms in the different nodes of a cluster. One probe is deployed for each node. If additional nodes are created on-demand, new probes will be created.
data_communicati on.py	Source file to handle different configuration options to expose the metrics gathered for the probe.
network_probe.py	Main source file of the probe, which contains the logic of the measurements, and the execution of the communication and exposure of the metrics.

3.3.2.1.1.3 Selected Technologies

The current version of netma-nsm-npp has considered the following technologies:

- **iPerf3²⁹** is a network testing tool that measures the maximum TCP and UDP bandwidth performance. It is widely used for network performance tuning and troubleshooting. The tool allows users to create data streams to measure the bandwidth between two endpoints in a network. iPerf3 supports various parameters, such as setting the test duration, adjusting the TCP window.
- **ICMP Ping.** Ping is a network utility tool used to test the reachability of a host on an Internet Protocol (IP) network. It works by sending Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) Echo Request messages to the target host and waiting for an Echo Reply. This process helps measure the round-trip time for messages sent from the originating host to a destination computer. Ping provides information about packet loss and network latency, which is essential for diagnosing network connectivity issues and performance.

3.3.2.1.1.4 Pre-requisites

- An active cluster with at least one worker node.
- Requirements are defined in the [requirements.txt](#) for installation and execution.

3.3.2.1.1.5 Installation Guide

The overall set up of netma-nsm-npp can be found in its [README](#). Execution and deployment of the probe is done via a daemonset of K8s, which deploys many services as nodes available in the cluster. This file is called [daemonset.yaml](#). Code execution flow is presented in Figure 21, considering main execution thread per node.daemonset.yaml.

3.3.2.1.1.6 Inputs and Outputs

- Input to netma-nsm-npp is offered via CLI commands, to personalize the metrics expected.

Output corresponds to the metrics required, that are exposed to Prometheus. By default, [NODE_IP]:5000/metrics.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 21: Flow-chart of the sub-component netma-nsm-npp.

3.3.2.1.2 netma-nsm-mon

3.3.2.1.2.1 Implementation Details

[netma-nsm-mom](#) has been based on the existing open-source code of the [K8s netperf](#) licensed under Apache 2.0. The current implementation provides CODECO with the following networking metrics: i) bandwidth; ii) latency; iii) packet loss; iv) jitter; v) node degree; vi) link failures; vii) link energy.

netma-nsm-mon is set by CODECO on each worker node and is based on two specific pods (K8s-netperf pod deployed in a passive state with a specific tool to be used to collect networking metrics, e.g., iPerf; specific pod actively engaged in real-time network monitoring by invoking specific probing tools). The output is periodically collected to a ConfigMap (currently, the default and configurable update interval is set to five minutes).

Metrics are collected from a node based on based on the Python's [asyncio](#)³² package for asynchronous operations allows for concurrent monitoring of different network parameters.

3.3.2.1.2.2 Code Structure

The main source code files of [netma-nsm-mon](#) are summarized in Table 18.

Table 18: Description of the main netma-nsm-mon source code files.

File	Function
K8s-netperf/netperf-netperf-2.7.0	Contains the source code of the K8s Netperf plugin , but config files have been updated to configure it for ARM64 architecture compatibility.
K8s-netperf/Dockerfile	Creates a Docker image for the Netperf pod, including various network tools such as iperf, netperf, and fortio.

32 <https://docs.python.org/3/library/asyncio.html>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

File	Function
K8s-netperf/k8s-netperf.yaml	Launches the different containers of netma-nsm-mon in the selected K8s cluster: A daemon set with host networking to test host-to-host network performance (which is typically, unaffected by the network plugin). A daemon set attached by the CNI network plugin to test its performance. Two other pods so that you will have two nodes with multiple PODs to test intra-node performance
K8s-netperf/run.sh	Executes when the Netperf container starts, launching three main network performance test services: the netperf server (netserver), two iperf servers (UDP and TCP modes), and the fortio server.
Monitoring/network_probe.py	Used for real-time network monitoring and converting the obtained network information into ConfigMap.

3.3.2.1.2.3 Selected Technologies

The current version of netma-nsm-mon has considered the following technologies:

- **K8s netperf³³**. K8s Netperf is a benchmarking tool designed to measure various aspects of networking performance, focusing on bulk data transfer and request/response performance using TCP or UDP with the Berkeley Sockets interface. It supports tests over IPv4 and IPv6, and can be used on multiple platforms, including Unix, Linux, and Windows. It provides an effortless way to test network performance between pods using various metrics. To deploy, apply the provided YAML file which sets up daemon sets and pods to measure host-to-host, pod-to-pod (intra- and inter-node), and pod-to-service (ClusterIP) performance. It is currently used for network latency testing based on the TCP protocol.
- **iPerf3**. In the current netma-nsm-mon version it is used for bandwidth and packet loss testing based on the UDP protocol.
- **ICMP Ping**. It is currently used for connectivity testing to monitor node degree and link failure states.
- **TCPdump**. TCPdump is a powerful command-line packet analyzer used for network troubleshooting and security auditing. It captures and displays the contents of network packets transmitted over a network in real-time, allowing users to diagnose network issues and understand the data being transferred. TCPdump supports filtering criteria to capture specific types of traffic, making it a versatile tool for network administrators and security professionals. It can analyze protocols such as TCP, UDP, and ICMP, providing detailed insights into network activity. Used for packet capture and analysis to calculate link energy.
- **Python asyncio**. Python's asyncio for asynchronous operations, ensuring simultaneous and orderly recording of multiple network parameters.

3.3.2.1.2.4 Pre-requisites

- An active cluster with at least two worker nodes.

3.3.2.1.2.5 Installation Guide

The overall set up of netma-nsm-mon can be found in its [readme](#). To run the netma-nsm-mon sub-component, first deploy the [k8s-netperf.yaml](#) file. This will create a set of K8s netperf pods that contain the necessary network measurement tools. Then, execute the [Monitoring/network_probe.py](#) file to start real-time network monitoring. The detailed code flow of network_probe.py is shown in Figure 22.

³³ <https://github.com/vtrocelab/netperf-2.7.0/tree/master>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 22: netma-nsm-mon flow-chart.

3.3.2.1.2.6 Inputs and Outputs

- Input to netma-nsm-mon are the networking underlay metrics being monitored.
- Output are the generated networking metrics (ConfigMap).

3.3.2.2 Nemesys: Network Exposure System

3.3.2.2.1 Implementation details

The steps followed by [Nemesys](#) once it is deployed in a cluster is provided in **Error! Reference source not found.** Once it is deployed in a cluster is to establish a connection with the NetMA Prometheus pod³⁴. NetMA resources are deployed together. Hence, each *IP:port peer* (worker nodes being monitored) currently has to be statically defined, being a parameter to include in the configuration files.

Once the connection with the NetMA Prometheus is established, Nemesys starts reading the CODECO network metrics (which have been captured by NSM and integrated into the local

³⁴ In the current version, for the sake of an agile deployment, NetMA relies on its specific Prometheus pod and not on the CODECO pod. Rf. To the Open Issues.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Prometheus), mapping the entries' names obtained from Prometheus with the metrics to expose. The output is provided in the CRD [netma-topology-metrics.yaml](#). As explained in NSM, NetMA performs monitoring at two networking levels, overlay and underlay. As both underlay and overlay monitoring tools use K8s-based identifiers, names will match. Also, the links have been defined using the format "source" + "_" + "destination".

Once the different network views and all the metrics associated to their status are available, they are integrated into the CRD [netma-topology-metrics.yaml](#) to create the CR to be pushed.

In this metrics translation it will be checked if all the needed information is available, and if not, it is evaluated if it is possible to replace them as it follows:

- If the missing information is a metric or a set of metrics, they are defined as zero during the information load, being therefore introduced as zero or void in the CR.
- If the missing information is a node/link/path, this information is not presented in the CR.
- If the missing information relates with an underlay metric, the corresponding overlay metric value will be used.
- If there is missing information for an attribute both at an overlay and underlay level, then no information is returned.

3.3.2.2 Code Structure

The Nemesys code is available at [NetMA/network-exposure](#). Its main source code files are summarized in Table 19.

Table 19: Nemesys source code files.

File	Function
nemesys.py	Core code for this component. It includes the code to launch the rest of the internal dependencies in nemesys module and the management of parameters.
requirements.txt	Document with Python dependencies.
kuberfiles/	folder with the resources to be deployed:
kuberfiles/00-namespace.yaml	Definition of he-codeco-netma namespace.
kuberfiles/01_netma-topology-crd.yaml	NetMA's CRD file.
kuberfiles/02_alto-deployment.yaml	ALTO's K8s version. Not used in the current release (CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit v2.0)
kuberfiles/03_alto-service.yaml	ALTO's exposure service definition. Not used in the current release (CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit v2.0)
Tests/	List of examples for internal request. Useful for testing.
Dockerfile	Definition to dockerize Nemesys module. Not required in the current release (CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit v2.0)
netma-topology-metrics.yaml	Example of the current CR.
.gitlab-ci.yml	CICD document to test the component. It also includes how to deploy the continent, with the format of the desired parameters

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 23: Nemesys workflow diagram.

3.3.2.2.3 Selected Technologies

This module has been implemented in Python v3.7. Input and output are based on YAML (CR) and Prometheus.

3.3.2.2.4 Pre-requisites

- K8s active cluster with at least two worker nodes and a master node.
- Python 3.7
- List of software requirements as in [requirements.txt](#).
- Device MUST have at least one network card, with internet connectivity

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- CODECO framework installed. Network exposure requires the other NetMA components to be installed, and ACM.

3.3.2.2.5 Installation Guide

A detailed description is provided in the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab (NetMA/Network Exposure) [README.md](#).

Download the respective code:

```
git clone git@gitlab.eclipse.org:eclipse-research-labs/codeco-
project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-exposure.git
```

Ensure the requirements and ecosystem are set:

```
python3 -m venv .venv && source ./venv/bin/activate
pip3 install -r requirements.txt
```

Deploy the resources:

```
kubectl apply -f kuberfiles/00-namespace.yaml
kubectl apply -f kuberfiles/01_netma-topology-crd.yaml
```

With these steps the code should be available in testing mode. Please notice that this code is expected to be deployed with the rest of the NetMA components as it has dependencies with them. Otherwise, if the intention is testing an isolated deployment, it is possible to check the functionality using the `-t` parameter, that will use the local files located in `test/` folder to check the functionality of the sub-component.

The main configuration parameters for Nemesys are provided in Table 20.

Table 20: Configuration parameters in Nemesys.

Parameter	Description	Values
<code>--acm</code>	URL where we are pushing the metrics to ACM.	"http://1.2.3.4:9090/api"
<code>--l2sm</code>	URL where the overlays metrics are being read from. <u>To be integrated under --prometheus parameter.</u>	"92.168.0.1:8080"
<code>--probes</code>	URL where the underlays metrics are being read from. <u>To be integrated under --prometheus parameter.</u>	"92.168.0.1:9090"
<code>--prometheus</code>	URL where the internal DB is launched. In the moment of the code release this parameter is split into <code>--acm</code> and <code>--probes</code> , <u>expecting to finalise this API integration before end of September 2024.</u>	"1.2.3.4:9090/"
<code>--metrics</code>	List of metrics used. In Prometheus there could be more metrics to be used internally, therefore we should count with the list of metrics to use once they are read.	["net_jitter_ms", "net_rtt_ms", "net_throughput_kbps"]
<code>--delay</code>	Seconds between CR updates	300

3.3.2.2.6 Inputs and Outputs

Nemesys has two inputs and two outputs to be considered, as shown in Table 21. However, the inputs could be extended if needed, adding future customized functions.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Table 21: Nemesys Input & Output.

Module	In/Out	Information
L2SM (via internal DB)	Input	Overlay metrics and its values. This input is from internal interfaces.
NSM (via internal database)	Input	Underlay metrics (and its values) and transport topology. This input is from internal interfaces.
ACM (via Prometheus)	Output	Integrated metrics for both overlay and underlay, following the JSON scheme defined in section 5.1.5. ACM – NetMA. This output is exported via the I-ACM-NET-1 interface.
NetMA CR	Output	NetMA topology (overlay and underlay) with its metrics, following the CR scheme defined in section 5.1.9. PDLC – NetMA. This output is exported via the I-NET-PDLC-1 interface.

3.3.2.3 L2S-M: Secure Connectivity

3.3.2.3.1 Implementation Details

The version of [L2S-M in the CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit v2.0](#) follows the architectural design described in D12 and again represented in Figure 24 addressing the implementation of the two main lines delineated: the collection of the performance metrics supported by the L2S-M overlay network (which are fed to Nemesys), and the CR/CRD interface for interacting with other CODECO modules (e.g., SWM). The collection of performance metrics at an overlay level is provided by the [L2S-M NPM](#) sub-component, which automatically collects available bandwidth, latency and jitter for any established K8s channel between pods. In addition, it is prepared to flexibly incorporate additional measurements, as well as the period over which such measures are conducted.

Figure 24. Secure Connectivity Design.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Additional components of L2S-M are the **L2S-M Control Plane**, encompassing the **CR/CRD interface** to interact with other CODECO components; the **SDN Controller**³⁵ to support the creation of virtual network across the overlay; and the metrics collector and exporter of the L2S-M Performance Measurements (LPM) component. This plane has been implemented as part of the L2S-M operator, conforming the communication channel between the SDN Controller, the K8s API and the L2S-M database, and redefining how virtual networks are created to allow pods use them. To this later, the operator offers a new a new type of networks, the Vlinks, which supports the path selection to steer the packets across the overlay in the bidirectional communications of two workloads.

Moreover, the operator comprises a CRD Controller (a K8s Controller Manager) that actively utilizes an internal K8s API to continuously communicate with the SDN Controller, and to maintain an accurate representation of the Virtual Network's status, while enabling the other components the usage of the L2S-M component through K8s CRDs.

3.3.2.3.2 Selected Technologies

This NetMA sub-component employs the following technologies:

- **L2S-M**³⁶, which implements a K8s operator to enable link-layer virtual networking in K8s clusters.
- **LPM**, based on Prometheus and developed using the programming language Go.
- **SDN Onos**³⁷. Java applications are developed conforming an SDN Controller that will be used by the subcomponent.
- **Kubebuilder**³⁸: this K8s framework is used to create this sub-component's API. This includes the K8s client that manages these resources, the CR Controller for the L2Networks CRD and the Pods Controller and Webhook, that will manage pods deployed using the L2S-M tool. By using this technology, L2S-M is able to catch the pods that are being launched into the cluster, add the required interfaces and connect them to the desired L2Network.
- **Open vSwitch**³⁹: virtual switch software used to create and implement the overlay topology inside the cluster. A minimal Go package is created wrapping the OVS v2.17 functionality.

3.3.2.3.3 Pre-requisites

- A K8s cluster with at least two worker nodes.
- Multus CNI installed⁴⁰.
- The Cert-Manager Plugin installed that will be used to deploy the Pod Webhook.

3.3.2.3.4 Installation guide

An installation guide of this sub-component is detailed in the [Secure Connectivity repository](#).

The installation process goes like this:

1. Install the required pre-requisites, the Multus CNI Plugin and the Cert-Manager.
2. Remove the node taints, so the control plane can be used to deploy pods:

35 Based on SDN ONOS

36 <https://github.com/Networks-it-uc3m/L2S-M>

37 <https://github.com/opennetworkinglab/onos>

38 <https://github.com/K8s-sigs/kubebuilder>

39 <https://www.openvswitch.org/>

40 Please notice that the CODECO operator already installs this dependency. It is here mentioned for the case of individual testing of the component.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

```
kubectl taint nodes --all node-role.k8s.io/control-plane- node-  
role.k8s.io/master-
```

3. Label the control-plane node as the "control-plane" of the cluster:

```
kubectl label nodes [control-plane-node] dedicated=control-plane
```

4. A deployment must be created in the Cluster which will install all the required components, by using the following command:

```
kubectl create -f ./deployments/l2sm-deployment.yaml -n=he-codeco-  
netma
```

After the installation, an overlay topology must be specified as shown in the installation [guide](#), with the desired links and nodes.

Then, the performance measurements module (LPM) must be deployed, as shown in the [LPM module installation guide \(rf. to NetMa/Secure Connectivity/LPM\)](#) In this case, and as explained in the guide, LPM utilizes to specify as values the name of the nodes and the metrics to be measured.

3.3.2.3.5 Inputs and Outputs

To better clarify the inputs expected by the Secure Connectivity module, an in-depth example is included in the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab, under [secure-connectivity/examples/ping-pong](#).

Security Connectivity gets as an input **the L2Network to be created**. Using the L2Network CRD, and using the type: Vlink field, other components can create a Virtual Link network (Vlink), specifying the vlink name, desired path and endpoint nodes. The in-depth example of the repository includes in the 'Creating a Vlink Network' section an example of how to define a L2Network resource. In particular, this resource allows to specify the path of L2S-M overlay nodes to be used in the communications between two pods. Once the L2Network is created in the cluster, pods can be attached to it using the annotation "*l2sm/networks: [{"name": "<vlink-name>", "ips": ["<static-ip-address>"}]}*", where the "<vlink-name>" parameter refers to the Vlink where we aim to attach the pod, and "<static-ip-address>" the IP address to be configured in the pod to establish the communications across the Vlink. With this information, the L2S-M component will append a new network interface in the pod, with the desired ip address, using that specified vlink. The in-depth example also shows how to define this operation.

There are three main fields must be specified in the pod for its deployment attached to a particular Vlink:

- .metadata.labels.l2sm: "true"
- .annotations.l2sm/networks: [<array of L2networks to be used, with an optional IP Address>]
- .spec.nodeName: <name of the node where the pod is going to be deployed. Must one of the vlinks endpoints.

The Secure Connectivity module has as output the **Overlay Network topology**, with its performance measurements (CRD). For this:

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- The LPM component stores information in the NetMA Prometheus database of the specific links in the overlay topology, with the unidirectional metrics. Jitter, available throughput and RTT are presented this way. These are stored with this syntax:
 - `net_jitter_ms_<link_hash>source_node="NodeA",target_node="l2s-m2"} <value>`
 - `net_rtt_ms_<link_hash>{source_node="NodeA",target_node="l2s-m2"} <value>`
 - `net_throughput_kbps_<link_hash>{source_node="NodeA",target_node="l2s-m2"} <value>`
- A CR exporter exists, enabling LPM to export these metrics outside the Prometheus database, using CRD specifications, enabling the update of the Status of the Overlay to the SWM component, using their NetworkTopology CRD.

3.3.3 NetMA Code Open Issues

Table 22 provides a list of code open issues for NetMA, which are expected to be handled in the next release (M24).

Table 22: NetMA code open issues.

ID	Description
NetMA-OI-1	Close the internal integration in a unified way. Currently each component has one interface (Prometheus, API/rest) to expose the metrics, but the idea is to integrate all the metrics in a unified way as described in Error! Reference source not found. Expected Deadline: M20.
NetMA -OI-2	There is a need of unification, synchronization and automatization of Network probes. It should be realized an integration process to achive this even though the main goal will be to have independent and customizable probes. This open issue will have two main lines: to consolidate the common data model for all probes and to select/manage the probes to be used during compilation time. Expected Deadline: M20.
NetMA -OI-3	Automatization of NetMA deployment in an integrated way: Having a unique deployment configuration file with the different parameters and commands needed to deploy each NetMA sub-component. <u>Expected Deadline: M23.</u>
NetMA -OI-4	Worst case scenario. We are currently testing the main workflow, but we need also to define how to act if there are complications or failures, both internal and external. <u>Expected Deadline: M23.</u>

3.4 MDM: Metadata Manager

3.4.1 Component Description

The CODECO MDM component collects, links, and enriches metadata related with the applications to be deployed across Edge-Cloud. This metadata assists in better characterizing the application deployment across Edge-Cloud. MDM is therefore a CODECO component that acts as a gateway between the data world (data workflow) and the K8s infrastructure (compute).

MDM and its sub-components are illustrated in Figure 25. MDM collects metadata from any “native system” that has information on the data, including data stores, catalogues, pipelines that copy and transform data, use-case specific functions that analyse the data, or any other relevant system. For this purpose, MDM relies on **connector interfaces** for each specific data type (I-MDM-E-1).

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 25: MDM sub-components and APIs to other components.

An MDM connector interfaces to a native data system or CRD and pushes metadata into a knowledge graph through the native (internal) MDM API. By adding new connectors or expanding the graph model, the system can be extended to collect any required metadata.

MDM is event-based, relying on Apache Kafka⁴¹. MDM relies on the Kafka event queue, a log of metadata events that occur for an Edge-Cloud setting managed with CODECO. Events describe changes that have happened and correspond to insert/update/delete of metadata entities and relationships.

MDM materializes (subsets of) the event queue in the knowledge graph to meet the needs of other CODECO components.

MDM is implemented by three components:

- **MDM API:** Implements the REST APIs that allow metadata to be pushed into the graph database and the graph to be queried.
- **Graph Database:** Stores the metadata graph.
- **Connectors:** They gather metadata and push it into the Graph Database using the MDM Controller APIs.

3.4.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation and Integration

3.4.2.1 Graph Database

The Graph Database ([MDM/Graphdb](#)) is the backend storage of the MDM component. The metadata events from all MDM connectors are consolidated here, making it possible for other components to extract insights from the distributed system from a single pane of glass. It is, of course, possible to request information by directly querying the database using cypher, but other than during development or exploration of the metadata, the MDM component is designed to offer this functionality through the MDM API.

⁴¹ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.4.2.1.1 Code structure

The main source files of the MDM GraphDB are presented in Table 23.

Table 23: Description of the main MDM GraphDB source code files.

File	Function
deployment/neo4j-helm.yaml	Example values to deploy the Neo4j Helm chart
Schemas/eu.codecohe/**/*_json	JSON schemas for the entities and relationships in the Knowledge Graph

3.4.2.1.2 Selected Technologies

The graph database is implemented using Neo4j:

- **Neo4j 4.4⁴²** or higher.
- **Neo4j APOC⁴³**: Awesome Procedures on Cypher (APOC) is an add-on library for Neo4j that provides hundreds of procedures and functions adding a lot of useful functionality.
- **Cypher Graph Query language⁴⁴**: Cypher is a declarative graph query language that allows for expressive and efficient data querying in a property graph. It is the query language for Neo4j and the language `opencypher45` is based on.
- **JSON Schema**: It is used to define the entities, their properties, and relationships among them in a language-independent manner. The schemas are available online⁴⁶.

3.4.2.1.3 Pre-requisites

Detailed pre-requisites for running Neo4j in K8s can be found from the vendor directly⁴⁷. CODECO relies on Neo4j's Community Edition. Commercial utilization of Neo4j's Enterprise Edition may require a license from the vendor. Please see <https://neo4j.com/licensing/> for details.

3.4.2.1.4 Installation Guide

To install the [Graph database](#) refer to the Helm chart provided by Neo4j. The following steps are detailed in the [online documentation in Git](#):

1. Set the following environment variables:

```
export MDM_NAMESPACE=mdm
export MDM_CONTEXT=docker-desktop
```

2. Add Neo4j's Helm chart to the Helm repositories:

```
helm repo add neo4j https://helm.neo4j.com/neo4j
```

3. Update the yaml configuration file for your K8s environment (online version neo4j-helm.yaml)

- set the `neo4j.password` for the database user `neo4j`
- define the volumes `StorageClass` if required.

⁴² <https://neo4j.com/>

⁴³ <https://neo4j.com/labs/apoc/>

⁴⁴ <https://neo4j.com/developer/cypher>

⁴⁵ <http://opencypher.org>

⁴⁶ https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb/-/tree/main/schemas/eu.codecohe?ref_type=heads

⁴⁷ <https://neo4j.com/docs/operations-manual/current/K8s/quickstart-standalone/Pre-requisites/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- adjust other parameters such as CPU and memory usage as required.

4. Install the Helm chart:

```
helm --kube-context=$MDM_CONTEXT install mdm-neo4j -n
$MDM_NAMESPACE neo4j/neo4j-standalone -f ./deployment/neo4j-
helm.yamlf
```

3.4.2.1.5 Inputs & Outputs

The Graph database is fed metadata events from Kafka by the mdm-controller subcomponent and offers a Cypher API to the mdm-api subcomponent. These interfaces are internal to MDM and declared here only for completeness.

3.4.2.2 MDM Controller (APIs)

The MDM controller provides the APIs for other CODECO components to query the metadata graph and for MDM connectors to provide metadata. The MDM Controller is thus a required sub-component for all scenarios where metadata analysis is required for the CODECO use-case. A selected set of MDM connectors depending on the use-case will provide metadata that allows through this subcomponent, allowing other CODECO components like PDLC to get summarize information about the systems and data in the form of parameters to models that provide the best scheduling for a given workload.

3.4.2.2.1 Code Structure

Table 24 and Table 25 provide a summary of the main MDM Controller source code files.

Table 24: Description of the main MDM Controller source code files.

File	Function
deployment/*.yaml	Example values to deploy the Kafka, Zookeeper and Neo4j Helm charts
controller/src/helm	Helm chart for the MDM controller
controller/src/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM controller
controller/src/python/ctrl.py	Main program for the MDM controller
controller/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM controller image
controller/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM controller

Table 25: Description of the main MDM API source code files.

File	Function
mdm-api/src/helm	Helm chart for the MDM API
mdm-api/src/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM API
mdm-api/src/python/app.py	Main program for the MDM API
mdm-api/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM API image
mdm-api/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM API

3.4.2.2.2 Selected Technologies

The MDM metadata collection has materialized in data systems that make it convenient to manage and exploit the metadata. The key technologies used in the current MDM Controller implementation include:

- **Apache Kafka:** Distributed event store and stream processing.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- Apache ZooKeeper⁴⁸, for the overall Kafka management and coordination (e.g., configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization).
- **Python 3.9** or higher for the implementation of the APIs and the interaction with Kafka and the Graph database.
- **OpenAPI 3.0** as the standard for the REST API for both input and output.
- **Swagger** as the mechanism to programmatically produce the REST API implementation designs and their documentation.

3.4.2.2.3 Pre-requisites

No specific hardware requirements are needed to run the MDM Controller. The Graph database component needs to be installed first.

3.4.2.2.4 Installation Guide

The Graph database needs to be installed first. After that, the order of installation of the MDM Controller sub-components is important:

- **mdm-zookeeper:** This is the MDM zookeeper sub-component, installed using Helm from the Bitnami⁴⁹ chart repository. This is required by the mdm-kafka sub-component.
- **mdm-kafka:** This is the MDM Kafka sub-component, installed using Helm from the Bitnami chart repository. This is required by the mdm-ctrl sub-component.
- **mdm-controller:** The MDM API Controller sub-component. Receives the metadata events from Kafka and pushes them into the Graph database.
- **mdm-api:** Implements the MDM REST API to the Graph database and connector publication API.

Detailed installation information is provided in the [MDM API GitLab repository](#).

When developing the MDM subcomponents, the docker build and push description provided in the online documentation require providing the docker registry used to store the images. This, as well as the tag, may change when new versions are developed. Assuming that the mdm-api repository has been cloned locally and is the current directory, the following steps are the basis to install MDM:

- **Install the MDM controller: If you need to change the tag of the docker image, or any other value, provide it in your own YAML file.**

```
cd mdm-controller
helm --kube-context=$MDM_CONTEXT -n $MDM_NAMESPACE install mdm-
controller ./mdm-controller/src/helm [-f my_values.yaml]
```

- **Install the MDM API: If you need to change the tag of the docker image, or any other value, provide it in your own YAML file.**

```
cd mdm-api
helm --kube-context=$MDM_CONTEXT -n $MDM_NAMESPACE install mdm-api
./mdm-api/src/helm [-f my_values.yaml]
```

The Helm charts for the installation of the mdm-controller and mdm-api sub-components may become available in the future from an online Helm repository.

⁴⁸ <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://github.com/bitnami/charts/tree/main/bitnami>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.4.2.2.5 Inputs & Outputs

Events consist of an event envelope and a payload. While the envelope structure is given by MDM, the payload types are application specific. Payloads are either entities or relationships with minimal restrictions on their structure, i.e., they need to contain a type and unique identifier(s). Entities and relationships are defined in JSON schema for CODECO at [MDM/graphdb/schemas/eu.codecohe](https://mdm.graphdb/schemas/eu.codecohe).

The MDM API is based on OpenAPI REST (OAS REST API) and integrates the following endpoint groups:

- **Publish** which is the endpoint for connectors writing to the MDM.
- **Events** which is the endpoint to get events from MDM.
- **Graph** gets information by querying the data projection. Initially this would allow for Cypher queries to be performed on the knowledge graph. If because of the experience gained with partners the set of queries required for the CODECO operation can be defined in a closed set, they can be incorporated to this API at a later stage.
- **MDM** is the system information endpoint for getting status and resets or other system relevance functions.
- **PDLC** is the endpoint where the PDLC component can query the graph for specific metrics related to the pods in the CODECO application.

All endpoints are protected and authorized usage enabled. The complete description is in swagger online documentation in MDM at the CODECO Eclipse GitLab (mdm-api/src/python/templates/swagger.yaml). Furthermore, note that the following API groups are not implemented, and responses will always be HTTP status 200 (OK): Groups, Lookup, Registration, Schemas and Versions.

Inputs:

POST /publish/event

Accept in the body a JSON structured event. The event payload object could be an entity or relationship structure.

Outputs:

GET /graph/entity/type

Get a JSON array of existing entity types in the metadata graph.

POST /graph/entity/type/{entitytype}

Get a list of entities in the metadata graph depending on the POST request JSON filter definition.

GET /graph/entity/attributes/{entitytype}

Get a JSON array of all existing attributes in the metadata graph for a given entity type.

GET /graph/path/{edf_id}

Get the graph structure as a JSON object for an entity identified by edf_id. As optional query parameter one can define the number of hops (depth) around the entity that will be included in the resulting graph.

POST /graph/cypher

The POST request body accepts a plain text base CYPHER query. The response will be the default JSON structure produced by the Graph database (Neo4j).

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

For example:

Request-body:

```
MATCH (a:compute)-[r]-(b) WHERE b.user_id = "Brandy.Neal@example.com" RETURN  
a as compute LIMIT 1
```

Response:

```
{  
  "identity": 4,  
  "labels": [  
    "compute",  
    "entity",  
    "visible"  
  ],  
  "properties": {  
    "_domain": "default",  
    "identifier": "AFCF2B98D7",  
    "serialNumber": "none",  
    "city": "Zurich",  
    "ritssDataClassification": "RII unclassified (Non-Confidential)",  
    "_status": [],  
    "networkClassification": "General Internal Enterprise Network",  
    "country_code": "CH",  
    "update_time": "2023-04-24T07:54:41.596286000Z",  
    "entity_type": "compute",  
    "dataClassification": [  
      "Public"  
    ],  
    "name": "srv-22",  
    "connector_id": "d79df9ea-efac-360c-b7cc-2cf0de386100",  
    "exportClassification": "blue",  
    "edf_id": "523e2537-b717-34e0-b303-638b159d7fcb",  
    "_id": "523e2537-b717-34e0-b303-638b159d7fcb"  
  },  
  "elementId": "1"  
}
```

GET /mdm

Get the running version of the mdm-api sub-component.

GET /mdm/state

Get the state of the different sub-components (neo4j/kafka/ctrl/etc)

DELETE /mdm/clean

Delete all metadata in the MDM component. Use with caution, only meant for development and testing purposes.

GET /events/sse

Server-Sent Events API-based filtered events from the serialized graph queue in Kafka. This is meant for components that need to be notified of specific metadata events as they happen, as opposed to gathering the current state from querying the metadata graph at time intervals.

GET /pdlc

This endpoint gets the metrics associated with the pods required by PDLC following a CRD format. The parameters are as follows:

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- *cluster*: The name of the cluster where the pod is running.
- *namespace*: The namespace where the pod is running
- *pod*: The name of the pod
- *rnd*: (optional) If this is set to “true,” the API provides random values for all metrics.

The result is provided in JSON as a K8s CR.

The output properties are:

- *pod_name*: The name of the pod, as provided as input.
- *freshness*: How fresh the data processed by pod is (see Prometheus connector below)
- *compliance*: Level of compliance of the pod given where it is running (see Compliance connector below)
- *portability*: A metric of how robust the execution of the pod is where it is running (see K8s connector below).

3.4.2.2.6 UML Diagram

The momentary interaction between the CODECO components and MDM and among the MDM subcomponents is depicted in **Error! Reference source not found..**

Figure 26: Interaction between MDM subcomponents.

Note that the connectors interact with the K8s API and the Prometheus API to obtain metadata, and the PDLC component uses the MDM API to obtain the metrics obtained from that metadata.

3.4.2.3 Connectors

Connectors send metadata to MDM in the form of events. Events are structured JSON documents. An event contains the following elements:

- The event type, either “insert” or “delete.”
- An identifier that uniquely identifies the connector that issued the event.
- A timestamp.
- The payload, i.e., the metadata.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Metadata is sent as entities and relationships. MDM imposes a basic structure on both entities and relationships to ensure that metadata can be stored as a graph. Entities must have a globally unique identifier and a type. It is the task of the connector to assign these. In addition, entities contain arbitrary numbers of attributes. The mandatory elements of a relationship are source and target entity identifier as well as a type. Relationships do not carry attributes. MDM does not define or enforce a static data model. Instead, the graph data model is defined by the structure of the entities and relationships that are inserted into MDM.

Entities and relationships are defined in JSON schema for CODECO at [MDM/graphdb/schemas/eu.codecohe](https://mdm.graphdb.com/schemas/eu.codecohe).

3.4.2.3.1 Selected Technologies

Connectors may be implemented in any programming language, if they make metadata available following the data model of the application framework (in this case CODECO's) and use the MDM Controller API conventions to make it available to the Graph database.

In the context of CODECO, the following technologies are considered:

- **Python 3.9 or higher** is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK:** Available here⁵⁰, it provides YAML-based configuration, and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API.

3.4.2.3.2 Pre-requisites

MDM Connectors don't have any hardware requirements. The MDM Controller component needs to be installed first so that connectors can send the metadata events.

3.4.2.3.3 Installation Guide

MDM Connectors are installed using Helm charts. The parameters required depend on the source of metadata to be inspected by the connector, and thus cannot be listed extensively.

At a minimum, the following parameters need to be provided:

- **pathfinder.url:** The URL of the MDM API.
- **pathfinder.K8sUrl:** The Kube API of the K8s cluster where the connector runs.

For a complete list of parameters please refer to [pathfinder-python-sdk/ibm_pathfinder_sdk/pathfinderconfig.py](https://github.com/ibm-pathfinder-sdk/pathfinderconfig.py).

3.4.2.3.4 Inputs & Outputs

MDM Connectors get input from the source of metadata inspected. The output is always provided in the form of metadata events sent to the MDM API using the **/publish/event** POST request.

For CODECO, helper classes are provided for Python connectors in [connectors/metadata-model/src/main/python/](https://github.com/ibm-pathfinder-sdk/connectors/metadata-model/src/main/python/). This way, connector developers can use the MDM CODECO metadata model directly by instantiating these Python classes for entities and relationships.

⁵⁰ <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.4.2.4 CODECO Default connectors

Users of the CODECO framework can install any connectors they develop or use the MDM APIs to provide metadata into the system to compute metrics or other information for their own purposes. Out of the box, CODECO provides three connectors that provide the metadata for certain metrics that are used by the scheduling mechanism in PDLC to decide on the placement of the CODECO application. These connectors are described in the following sections.

3.4.2.4.1 K8s connector

Information about the K8s environment managed by CODECO is essential to provide meaningful decisions as to how to schedule CODECO applications. The K8s connector gets all entities in a K8s cluster and includes them in the MDM metadata graph, together with the relationships among them.

The K8s connector collects among other data the number of restarts of a pod, which is used as a proxy for the portability metric of that pod running in that cluster and namespace.

3.4.2.4.1.1 Code structure

Table 26 provides a summary of the main MDM K8s connector source code files.

Table 26: Main MDM K8s connector source code files.

File	Function
connectors/k8s/src/main/helm	Helm chart for the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/python/connector.py	Main program for the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/docker/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM K8sconnector
connectors/k8s/src/main/python/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM K8sconnector

3.4.2.4.1.2 Selected Technologies

The K8s connector is developed based on:

- **Python 3.9 or higher:** is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK:** Available online⁵¹, it provides YAML-based configuration, and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API
- **K8s watcher API:** This allows the K8s connector to receive as events all the entities created in the K8s cluster, including but not limited to pods, CRDs, deployments, etc.
- The K8s connector source code is available at [MDM/connectors/connectors/k8s/src/main](#).

3.4.2.4.1.3 Pre-requisites

The CODECO MDM K8s connector needs to run with enough privilege to get all events in a K8s cluster.

3.4.2.4.1.4 Installation Guide

The CODECO MDM K8s connector is installed using a Helm chart provided in the same repository where the code is available. Other than the default parameters required for all connectors, the following are required:

⁵¹ <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- **crawler.K8s.api_url**: The URL of the K8s API for the cluster being monitored.
- **crawler.K8s.sa_token**: If the connector is not running under a sufficiently privileged service account, the token with sufficient permissions to watch the K8s API must be provided in this parameter.

3.4.2.4.1.5 Inputs & Outputs

Using as input the events obtained by watching the K8s API, the K8s connector provides metadata about all K8s entities in the MDM graph following the metadata model described above.

3.4.2.4.2 Compliance connector

The level of compliance of a K8s environment managed by CODECO is another metric required to schedule CODECO applications. The Compliance connector uses Kubespace⁵² to obtain a metric of compliance of the cluster and adds that information to the MDM metadata graph.

3.4.2.4.2.1 Code structure

Table 27 provides a summary of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.

Table 27: Description of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.

File	Function
connectors/kubescape/src/main/helm	Helm chart for the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/python/connector.py	Main program for the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/docker/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM compliance connector
connectors/kubescape/src/main/python/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM compliance connector

3.4.2.4.2.2 Selected Technologies

The K8s connector is developed based on:

- **Python 3.9 or higher** is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK**: Available online⁵³, it provides YAML-based configuration, and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API
- **Kubespace**: Kubespace is an open-source technology that performs a number of tests (controls) following compliance rules from well-known security and compliance frameworks. By default, the MITRE and NSA frameworks are enabled⁵⁴, which perform controls on configuration of worker nodes, K8s API, etc., and provide a level of coverage as a percentage.

3.4.2.4.2.3 Pre-requisites

The CODECO MDM K8s connector needs to run with enough privilege to access configuration information through the K8s API.

52 <https://kubescape.io/docs/frameworks-and-controls/>

53 <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

54 <https://kubescape.io/docs/frameworks-and-controls/frameworks/>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.4.2.4.2.4 Installation Guide

The CODECO MDM Compliance connector is installed using a Helm chart provided in the same repository where the code is available. Other than the default parameters required for all connectors, the following are required:

- **crawler.K8s.api_url**: The URL of the K8s API for the cluster being monitored.
- **crawler.K8s.sa_token**: If the connector is not running under a sufficiently privileged service account, the token with sufficient permissions to obtain configuration information through the K8s API must be provided in this parameter.

3.4.2.4.2.5 Inputs & Outputs

Using as input the information available through the K8s API, the Compliance connector uses the Kubescape tool to provide a metric for the level of compliance of a K8s cluster and the worker nodes, which is attached to the corresponding MDM metadata graph entities.

3.4.2.4.3 Prometheus connector

CODECO components and use-cases may use Prometheus as a means to make certain metrics available. The MDM Prometheus connector obtains configured metrics from Prometheus to enrich entities in the metadata graph with those values. In particular, the “freshness” metric is captured such that if a CODECO application is to be scheduled according to that particular metric, making it available in CODECO’s Prometheus will make it possible for PDLC to schedule the application to optimize the “freshness” of the data being processed.

3.4.2.4.3.1 Code Structure

Table 28 provides a summary of the main MDM Compliance connector source code files.

Table 28: Description of the main MDM K8s connector source code files.

File	Function
connectors/prometheus/src/main/helm	Helm chart for the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/python/*.py	Python code for the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/python/connector.py	Main program for the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/docker/Dockerfile	Dockerfile to produce the MDM prometheus connector
connectors/prometheus/src/main/python/requirements.txt	Python dependencies of the MDM prometheus connector

3.4.2.4.3.2 Selected Technologies

The K8s connector is developed based on:

- **Python 3.9 or higher** is the preferred programming language, as it will allow the connector developer to leverage the open-source connector SDK.
- **IBM Pathfinder SDK⁵⁵** provides YAML-based configuration and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API.
- **Prometheus**: Prometheus is an open-source technology⁵⁶ that records metrics in a time series database built using a pull model, where an endpoint is made available for applications and Prometheus queries periodically the endpoint to obtain the metrics.

⁵⁵ <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk/>

⁵⁶ <https://prometheus.io>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.4.2.4.3.3 Pre-requisites

The CODECO MDM K8s connector needs the required credentials to access the Prometheus query endpoint. The Prometheus service needs to be integrated with K8s so that the association between the metric and the pod producing it can be obtained and reflected in the Knowledge Graph.

3.4.2.4.3.4 Installation Guide

The CODECO MDM Compliance connector is installed using a Helm chart provided in the same repository where the code is available. Other than the default parameters required for all connectors, the following are required:

- **crawler.k8s.api_url:** The URL of the K8s API for the cluster being monitored.
- **crawler.prometheus.server.url:** The hostname of the Prometheus query API
- **crawler.prometheus.server.port:** The port of the Prometheus query API
- **crawler.prometheus.metric:** The name of the metric to capture (default is *CODECO_freshness*)
- **crawler.prometheus.entity:** The name of the entity in the metadata graph to attach the metric to.

3.4.2.4.3.5 Inputs & Outputs

Using as input the values obtained through the Prometheus query API, an arbitrary metric can be attached to arbitrary entities in the MDM metadata graph.

3.5 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration

3.5.1 Component description

The CODECO SWM component handles the initial deployment, monitoring, and potential migration of application workloads within a single cluster and across multi-cluster environments. This implies assisting the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) placement of applications and their containers across Edge-Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (e.g., device and node availability; container centrality; network characteristics). The SWM handles, for instance, the “best” placement (based on context-awareness indicators) for the containerised components of an application to be deployed in a cluster, dealing with dynamic properties of available infrastructure, including physical/virtual machines as well as network nodes and links. Further, this placement shall be dynamically adaptable, which implies achieving the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) migration of containerised micro-services of an application, including their state, across Edge and Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (device and node availability; container centrality, network aspects).

The high-level view of the SWM component and its interfaces is shown in Figure 27.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Figure 27: SWM high-level representation.

SWM contains two subcomponents, each one in an own repository, the [QoS Scheduler](#) and the [Workload Placement Solver](#) (QoS Solver). The interface between the two is a [gRPC API](#) with data structure defined with *protobuf*. For further description of the functionality and the QoS Model, please see Deliverable D10.

SWM has the following pre-requisites:

- **Active K8s cluster:** versions: currently tested: v1.23-v1.29 on KinD cluster, v1.26 on kubespray bare-metal cluster.
- **CNI plugins (tested):** Weave, Calico (others should work as well, but were not yet tested).
- **Worker nodes HW architecture:** x86 (amd64), arm64
- **RBAC roles** according to Helm chart deployments required.
- **Tools installed:** kubectl, helm.
- **Access to K8s API** (kubeconfig file with access credentials).

SWM is installed using a Helm chart that is part of the implementation. The major steps are:

- Adapt Helm configuration files.
- Deploy Helm chart.
- Adapt and apply explicit network topology (K8s yaml file) – this is only required if Channel with dedicated QoS (Service class ASSURED) shall be used.
- Simple tests (e.g., list network links, deploy sample application and watch custom resources).

A concise description of required steps can be found in the [Quick Start](#) documentation in the CODECO SWM repository. A more detailed description of adaptation options can be found in the [Getting Started](#) file.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3.5.2 Sub-components' Specification, Implementation and Integration

3.5.2.1 QoS-Scheduler

The main usage scenario of the QoS Scheduler is to schedule Workloads (pods) of at least one Application, belonging to an ApplicationGroup. The detailed flow of this is described in Subsection **Error! Reference source not found.**, using a UML flowchart.

Figure 28 shows the subcomponents and the inner structure of the *QoS Scheduler* as currently implemented.

Figure 28: SWM QoS-Scheduler subcomponent structure.

The [SWM GitLab repository](#) contains the following directories:

- [build](#): ci files to build all containers.
- [Config/demo](#): yaml files for the demos.
- [Documentation](#): several pieces of documentation, background information, UML diagrams.
- [scheduler](#): the code for the custom resources and their controllers lives here, as well as the code for the network and optimizer services. Also, the directory contains the code for the custom scheduler plugin and the QoS CRD client.
- [Helm/gos-scheduler](#): the Helm chart and its subcharts for installing the entire system; the CRDs (yaml files).

The QoS Scheduler consists of the following subcomponents (see also **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- **ApplicationGroupController**: This is the controller for the CR ApplicationGroup. It handles the main flow and actions for scheduling and deploying all Applications (including their workloads and channels) of an ApplicationGroup, including calling the Workload Placement Solver to calculate a placement of the Workloads in the ApplicationGroup.
- **ApplicationController**: This is the controller for the CR Application.
- **IPAM Controller**: This is the controller for the CR IP Address Management (IPAM). It manages IP address ranges that are required when creating (small) overlay network segments that are needed for each Channel (if the data transfer goes via a specific CNI plugin, as is implemented for the “Topology CXR based” Network Operator).
- **AssignmentPlanController**: This is the controller for the CR AssignmentPlan. The AssignmentPlan is the interface towards the Workload Placement Solver. It contains the QoS Model (consisting of Application Model and Infrastructure Model) used to call the Workload Placement Solver, as well as the placement of Workloads to Worker Nodes and of the Channels to Network Paths once the Workload Placement Solver has returned a result.
- **Webhooks**: Validating webhook that checks some custom resources (mainly Channel) of the QoS Scheduler for duplicate names, valid syntax, etc.
- **Custom Scheduler**: This implements a K8s custom scheduler (with the name “QoSScheduler”) using the K8s scheduling framework. The go code implements plugins for the different scheduling phases. The Custom Scheduler is built and deployed to the K8s control plane (namespace kube-system).
- **NodeDaemon**: This is started as a daemonset in K8s and runs on every node. The NodeDaemon grabs the network configuration of all network interfaces of its node and writes the information into the CR NetworkEndpoint.
- **NetworkOperator**: A NetworkOperator is the component that interfaces with the network infrastructure. There can be multiple NetworkOperators, each managing a different so-called network implementation. A NetworkOperator creates and maintains the CRs CR NetworkLink and NetworkPath for its network implementation, which define the network topology. The SWM repo contains three implementations for a NetworkOperator:
 - **K8s-nwcontroller**: This is a quite simple NetworkOperator, which just reads the basic underlying K8s network (host network of K8s worker nodes), and creates a fully meshed network topology from this, assuming default network parameters. The respective ChannelController is a simple implementation as well. It does not do any sort of bandwidth management for the channels to be set up, it just acknowledges them.
 - **I2sm-nwcontroller**: This is an implementation of a NetworkOperator that interacts with NetMA in CODECO. It creates a network topology from a CR NetworkTopology, that is regularly updated by NetMA, and that contains the L2S-M overlay network that is set up to support controlled traffic in a cluster. The I2sm-nwcontroller makes reservations for L2S-M resources (vlinks) for each Channel. Data plane communication is handled via separate interfaces in the source and target Pods of the Channel, and it is managed by NetMA. A detailed description of the interaction between the SWM L2SM network operator and the NetMA L2S-M component is described in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**
 - **topology-nwcontroller**: This is an example implementation of a NetworkOperator that creates a network topology from a CR NetworkTopology, and that contains a more elaborate ChannelController, which handles the data plane via a CNI plugin.
- **ChannelController**: Manages the CR Channel. Whenever a Channel is created (which is done by the ApplicationGroupController), the ChannelController takes care about the progression of state. Potential functions of the ChannelController are: Managing

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

bandwidth for Channels, making reservations for Channels, creating the required resources for the data plane (handling CNI annotations/metadata that can be used by a CNI plugin to create a dedicated interface and routable data connection).

- **CNI Plugin VLAN:** An example implementation of a CNI plugin that sets up dedicated interfaces in the Pods for a Channel, and that uses Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) IDs and VLAN priorities to prioritize traffic that is sent through this data connection. The CNI plugin uses sub interfaces, veth pairs, and iptables to create an overlay network and routable data path for the Channel.

The QoS Scheduler is deployed as K8s workloads and resources on a K8s cluster. Some components (e.g., Node Daemon, CNI plugin) require access to the worker nodes and extended privileges for running the containers. This will not run on managed K8s clusters (such as AWS EKS).

Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs)

The [yaml files](#) of all SWM CRDs are generated from [go type definitions](#) that include kubebuilder annotations. This is done from the make file (*make manifests*).

3.5.2.1.1 Code Structure

The directories in the repository of the QoS-Scheduler contain the source code as listed in Table 29.

Table 29. SWM QoS-Scheduler code structure (Go packages).

File	Function
build	Build instructions and Docker files for CI containers and production containers.
config/demo	Deployment files to test the SWM QoS-Scheduler
helm/qos-scheduler	Helm charts to deploy SWM QoS-Scheduler and SWM QoS-Solver
scheduler/api/v1alpha1	Go type definitions for SWM CRDs (incl. kubebuilder annotations)
scheduler/application	Go package application. Implements the logic for the SWM CRDs related to the SWM application model.
scheduler/cmd	Go package main. Contains main functions for executables of all containers built for QoS-Scheduler (cni-vlan, controller, network-l2sm, network-K8s, network-topology, node-daemon, optimizer-stub, scheduler, validator)
scheduler/controllers	Go package controllers. Implements the controllers for the SWM CRDs (except network-related CRDs)
scheduler/infrastructure	Go package infrastructure. Implements infrastructure related base functionality.
scheduler/network	Implements base functionality and controllers for the network related CRDs. There are currently three network operators: K8s-nwcontroller, l2sm-nwcontroller, topology-nwcontroller.
scheduler/optimizer/client	Go package optimizerclient. Implements the client side gRPC interface to the Workload Placement Solver.
scheduler/schedulerplugins	Go package schedulerplugins. Implements the SWM qos scheduler plugins according to the K8s scheduler framework.
scheduler/webhooks	Go package webhooks. Implements a validating webhook, that validates user-provided Channel names.
scripts	Shell scripts used in CI/CD pipeline

3.5.2.1.2 Inputs and Outputs

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

QoS Scheduler defines CRs that clients use to describe the desired system state (i.e., which application and workload should be deployed).

All CRDs are however generated from Go source files using the tool kubebuilder⁵⁷. The Go files accessing the custom resources contain appropriate pragmas instructing kubebuilder to add simple fields or whole structures to a CRD.

If a CR needs to be changed (e.g., add a new field), the corresponding Go files are updated with the new field. Then the corresponding CRDs must be regenerated. Target “generate” of [scheduler/Makefile](#) does this. The following commands will update the Scheduler’s CRDs after changing a file:

```
# in Scheduler's project directory:
```

```
cd scheduler  
make generate
```

Inputs

The external inputs of the QoS Scheduler are mainly defined by custom resources⁵⁸ handled via the K8s API:

Inputs related to other CODECO components:

- CR ApplicationGroup
- CR Application
- CR Workload
- CR Channel
- CR NetworkEndpoint
- CR NetworkLink
- CR NetworkPath
- CR NetworkTopology

Inputs related to other SWM subcomponents (Workload Placement Solver):

- [optimizer.proto](#) (gRPC interface, protobuf definition part: Reply)

Internal inputs (configuration and operation purposes):

- CR IPAM (IP Address Management).

Outputs

Most of the external outputs of the QoS Scheduler can also be observed via custom resources and the K8s API.

Outputs related with K8s and other CODECO components:

- K8s Pod (created by SWM for Workloads)
- K8s Service (created by SWM for Channels)
- CR ApplicationGroup (status).
- CR Application (status)
- CR Workload (status)
- CR Channel (connection/reservation request, status)

⁵⁷ <https://github.com/kubernetes-sigs/kubebuilder>

⁵⁸ An overview and description of these CRs can be found in Deliverable D10. The yaml files for these CRDs can be found here.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- CR AssignmentPlan (scheduling decision of SWM)
- CR L2Network (network type “vlink”), defined by NetMA⁵⁹

Outputs related to other SWM subcomponents (Workload Placement Solver):

- [optimizer.proto](#) (gRPC interface, protobuf definition part: QoSModel).

The detailed CRDs can be found in the QoS Scheduler repository ([swm/qos-scheduler/helm/qos-scheduler/charts/qos-crds](#)). The CRDs files contain some more detailed descriptions inline.

The gRPC Interface and its data structure are defined by protobuf definitions, which can be found in the QoS Scheduler repo as well ([swm/qos-scheduler/scheduler/proto](#)).

3.5.2.2 Workload Placement Solver

The Workload Placement Solver (“Solver” for short) provided with CODECO is an example of a service performing the tasks shown below. The Solver is a simple component and does not have any sub-components. It performs the following main operations:

- Accepts a placement problem from the QoS Scheduler via the gRPC interface.
- Finds a solution for the given problem considering workload and network constraints using a backtracking algorithm.
- Returns the solution via the gRPC interface.

The gRPC interface allows the implementation of other workload placement solvers. The workload placement solvers to be used is a configuration parameter of QoS Scheduler. Using a different workload placement solver instead of Solver is easy.

The Solver’s backtracking algorithm searches for a solution using a heuristic to speed up the search. It stops at the first solution found that fulfils all constraints for all workloads and channels. The Solver may consider multiple solutions but does not optimize the solution in any way.

The Solver is stateless, i.e., it does not keep track on the workloads deployed in previous request. Solver handles each request independently from any other request. For the Solver, it is *not* important that the entities it should reason about are entities existing in the cluster Solver is running in.

In more technical terms: function *Solve()* handles incoming messages of type Request from a client (typically the QoS Scheduler). The request contains the so-called QoS Model that specifies an application and an infrastructure model. The former defines the applications and workloads and the communication channels between workloads including any resource constraints like CPU, memory, or bandwidth requirements. The latter defines the resources currently available on the cluster’s nodes and the topology of the network(s) connecting the nodes including the links’ bandwidths.

For every request, Solver computes a so-called placement and returns it in a message of type Reply. The interface is defined as a stream of replies, but the Solver sends only the first solution it finds. Other workload placement solvers can use of this feature to make intermediate solutions available to the client. A placement contains the following information:

- A node name for each workload that Solver assigned to a node.
- A path name for each channel that Solver assigned to a network path.

⁵⁹ Note that the SWM/QoS-Scheduler code also contains a type definition and the CRD yaml file for the L2Network CRD in order to be able to access the objects in go.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

The interface can manage workloads already running in the cluster. Specifying a node for a workload is necessary if this workload is the target of a channel starting from one of the workloads added to the cluster. When also specifying the requirements of the target workload, Solver can compute a placement that migrates a workload from one node to another.

3.5.2.2.1 Key Technologies

The SWM Solver is a simple application providing a service via a gRPC interface. No special tools or libraries are used in Solver's implementation. The modules and tools used for implementing command-line handling, unit tests, and overseeing the ProtoBuf packages sent and received via gRPC interface are in wide-spread use.

- Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC, TRL 9)
- Protocol Buffers (Protobuf, TRL 9).
- Go programming language (Golang, TRL 9).

The Solver runs within a K8s cluster but does not access the K8s API. Currently, the Solver is available for CPU architectures AMD64 and ARM64. As the Solver uses modules it requires at least version 1.11 of Go. At the time of writing Solver uses Go version 1.20.

3.5.2.2.2 Pre-requisites

The Solver is deployed to a K8s cluster usually via a Helm chart. The Solver does not have specific access requirements to custom resources as all data passed to Solver and returned to Solver's clients is sent via the gRPC interface. Its pre-requisites are:

- K8s cluster with nodes having CPU architecture AMD64 or ARM64. Solver has no specific requirements to the version of K8s used.
- Tools installed: kubectl and Helm.

Tools kubectl and Helm are only necessary to deploy Solver to a cluster. They are *not* needed when Solver is running in a cluster. Solver does not have any run-time dependencies to other services in a K8s cluster.

3.5.2.2.3 Installation

The Solver is installed in a cluster in combination with QoS Scheduler. Solver's Helm chart is currently part of Scheduler's Helm chart.

3.5.2.2.4 Inputs and Outputs

All input for and output from Solver is via the gRPC interface. All data on this interface are sent as message that are encoded using as ProtoBuf messages. Two files define the structure of the messages:

- File "[optimizer-service.proto](#)" defines services (i.e., functions) and messages for service "Scheduler". This is the public interface supported by Solver.
- File "[optimizer.proto](#)" defines the messages that make up an assignment problem that Solver should compute a solution for. Solver considers the problem as given in the request and nothing else. If Solver should take workloads already running in the cluster into account, they must be given in Solver's input.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

The Solver does *not* consider any anything besides the data given to it when solving the problem. It does for instance not read the set of nodes available in the cluster or refer to workloads that were placed in a previous request.

The QoS Scheduler owns both file “[optimizer-service.proto](#)” and file “[optimizer.proto](#)”, i.e., the master copy of those files is in Scheduler’s repository. They are copied to Solver’s repository for simplicity’s sake. If the master copy changes, the copy in the Solver’s repository needs to be updated.

3.5.2.2.5 Component Diagrams

Figure 29 shows how the components of Solver and Scheduler work together. The Solver’s component “solved” provides an interface for solving assignment problems. Solver’s component “solve”, and Scheduler use this interface to solve a given assignment problem. Scheduler needs to solve assignment problems that stem from deployments a user requested.

Figure 29: Interaction between Solver’s components and Scheduler.

3.5.2.2.6 Implementation

Solver is a Go module structured with respect to the guidelines outlined in Standard Go Project Layout⁶⁰. Table 30 contains the important packages and files in Solver’s module.

Table 30: Packages and files in Solver’s module.

Package/File	Description
.reuse	Folder with a control file for REUSE to check for copyright and license information in Solver’s files
build/ci	Context folders with files needed to build container images used for jobs in Solver’s pipeline running on GitLab CI.
build/package	Context folders with files needed to build container images for Solver’s deployment. In most cases only image “solved” is deployed to a K8s cluster.
cmd/solve	Implements command-line tool “solve” that verifies whether tool “solved” running in a cluster properly handles the gRPC interface.
cmd/solved	Implements command-line tool “solved”; a gRPC server with the QoS model interface, serving placement requests from the QoS-Scheduler.
docs	Folder with documentation files
internal	Go packages local to module Solver.
internal/port/grpc	Package providing functions and types for managing the message sent and received via the gRPC interface.
pkg	Go packages that may be used in other Go modules.
pkg/data	Package providing some simple assignment problems for testing.
pkg/solve	Package providing function Solve() for computing a solution to an assignment problem. This package implements the backtracking algorithm search for a solution.
pkg/textformat	Package providing a concise text format for specifying an assignment problem. The test format can be used with tool “solve” to pass an assignment problem to a workload placement solver running locally or in a cluster.

60 <https://github.com/golang-standards/project-layout>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Package/File	Description
scripts	Scripts for Solver's Makefile and pipeline.
testdata	Files with data for tests run when building Solver. At the time of writing there are about 480 tests for Solver.
.gitlab-ci.yml	Pipeline definition file
Makefile	File for GNU make with rules to build all images and deliverables of Solver. Everything for Solver is built using this file.

Figure 30 shows the dependencies between the Solver's packages. It contains only packages defined by the Solver. Third-party packages or packages from Go's standard library are not shown.

Figure 30: SWM Solver's package relationships.

The Solver's Makefile and pipeline work together building the Solver's executables. The pipeline definition does not define scripts for jobs but tells the Makefile to build the desired object. This setup avoids the problem that a local build differs from a pipeline build as different command sequences are used. In Solver everything that is built gets built using the Makefile regardless of whether the build happens on a developer's machine or by GitLab CI. For further details check the documentation of Solver's [Makefile](#) and [pipeline definition](#).

There are two special folders "deliv" and "tmp" Solver's Makefile and pipeline use to keep generated files. All files in folder "deliv" are products that should be kept. Examples for such files are binaries for Solver's command-line tools or an archive with Solver's HTML documentation.

Folder "tmp" is for all temporary files produced when building a final product. The strategy in Solver is to keep the source tree clean and put all temporary files in dedicated folder "tmp." A user can force a complete rebuild easily by deleting this folder.

3.5.3 SWM Open Issues

Table 31 provides a list of code open issues for SWM, which are expected to be handled in the next release.

Table 31: SWM Open-source code issues.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

ID	Description
SW-OI-1	Implement the re-scheduling of applications. Expected deadline: M22.

4 Experimentation Assisted Developments

4.1 CODECO Synthetic Data Generator

4.1.1 Component Description

A significant challenge encountered when introducing AI/ML tasks is the scarcity of realistic cluster monitoring data. Within the CODECO framework, benchmark metrics must be leveraged to achieve proactive resource adaptability and cross-layer orchestration. These metrics are generated and collected during the deployment and execution of the respective services within the defined infrastructure. To address this issue and assist the CODECO OSS Toolkit, the CODECO [Synthetic Data Generator](#) (CSDG) has been implemented. Detailed descriptions of its internal architecture, components, and functionality are provided in D10.

The SDG is designed to produce realistic benchmark data corresponding to the metrics described in D10, Annex I, enabling comprehensive testing of the functionalities offered by CODECO components. Installation, setup, and running instructions for the SDG are included to facilitate its integration and use. For instance, the CODECO-PDLC component, which employs an AI-based approach for behaviour estimation, requires enrichment with this synthetic data to perform all necessary operations and achieve its objectives.

4.1.2 Specification and Implementation Aspects

The CSDG seamlessly integrates with the CODECO infrastructure in its experimentation mode, leveraging the K8s API to access raw values in CR format. The CSDG aims to extract testing data for the ACM, MDM, and NetMA components within the CODECO framework. Upon installation, the CSDG initiates the creation of three CRDs along with their respective deployments. Each deployment is meticulously configured with permissions designed to facilitate the viewing, listing, and updating of CRs linked to the aforementioned CRDs. These deployments function as specialized controllers: a) ACM Controller: Manages ACM behavior data, b) MDM Controller: Manages MDM behavior data, c) NetMA Controller: Manages NetMA behavior data.

4.1.2.1 Pre-requisites

- An active K8s cluster, with at least two nodes (control-plane node and worker node).
- Administrative privileges must be granted on the cluster, including access to the default Service Account.

4.1.2.2 Installation guide

During the installation, it is essential to specify the nodes within the selected K8s cluster. A detailed example on how to specify the K8s cluster nodes is also provided in [CSDG](#). Furthermore, the changes to the respective YAML files ([netma-controller/netma-controller-deployment.yaml](#), [acmcontroller/acm-controller-deployment.yaml](#)) are also provided.

After performing the node specification based on the selected cluster's topology, the deployment of the controllers, is realized by performing the execution the following commands:

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

```
chmod -R 777 apply-controllers.s  
  
./apply-controllers.sh
```

To deploy mock CRDs for independent testing of the SDG (e.g., for use with PDLC), execute the following commands:

```
chmod -R 777 apply-dummy.sh./apply-dummy.sh
```

4.1.2.34.1.2.3. Inputs and Outputs

As previously noted, the CSDG interfaces with CODECO CRDs, accepting real-time CR values as input and generating a CSV file as output. This file includes time-series observations that describe the cross-layer metrics provided by CODECO components.

4.2 Facility Porting Artefacts

In this section, the progress made in supporting a reproducible and seamless approach to experimenting with CODECO components is discussed. To this end, the *CODECO Experimentation Framework (CODEF)* provides heterogeneous, multi-cluster, and multi-domain capabilities in an automated and declarative manner, reducing the need for operational support. Additionally, it supports the use of EdgeNet (software and testbed) as part of the experimentation options.

4.2.1 CODEF: CODECO Experimentation Framework

This subsection examines the CODECO Experimentation Framework, a microservice-based solution proposed and implemented by ATH for the experimentation of CODECO components in WP5. The framework focuses on the experimentation of containerized scenarios, particularly in edge cloud deployments and K8s environments, utilizing -among others- technologies such as Bash scripting, Ansible and Kubeadm.

Some of its main capabilities include:

- holistic experiment configuration.
- Reproducible experimentation automation.
- Distinct and independently extensible architectural abstraction layers, covering the complete experimentation process.
- Integration with heterogeneous external environments (i.e., bare metal, VirtualBox, EdgeNet, Cloudlab, Amazon Cloud) via distinct Infrastructure Managers.

Please refer to D10 [1] for a detailed description of the architecture and features of the CODECO Experimentation framework.

4.2.1.1 Code Structure

The [CODEF](#) is available in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab repository. Detailed instructions, teaser videos and demos can be found in the respective [README.md](#) files, and a summary of the main code source files are provided in Table 32.

The proof-of-concept results run with one-liner scripts (*.sh*) provided inside the repository ([experimentation-framework/codeco-experimentation-framework/](#)). These experiments were executed in on-premises servers with [XCP-ng hypervisor](#) (Xen-based) using the [XCP-ng Infrastructure Manager](#) (i.e. *infra_manager_type=xcp-ng* in the [cluster_deployment.sh](#) script), however different [Infrastructure Managers](#) are provided in CODEF (e.g., *vbox_im* or

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

cloudlab_im). Such proof-of-concept examples include extensive performance evaluation of native K8s components such as networking (CNI plugins); ML, *Anomaly Detection (AD)* and *Change Point (CP)* methods; deployment of complex software solutions like EdgeNet.

Commands to run: [./experiments-net.sh](#) (refers to the installation of CNI-plugins across different K8s distributions, some designed for the far Edge, the deployment of benchmark application and evaluation).

Commands to run: [./install-edgenet-cluster.sh](#) (refers to the installation of an upgraded version of EdgeNet software).

Table 32: Description of the main CODECO Experimentation framework source code files.

File	Function
codeco-exp-framework/configurations/example-configuration	Characteristics of the cluster(s) definition to be deployed
codeco-exp-framework/infrastructure-managers	Supported Infrastructure Managers to be installed and used
codeco-exp-framework/playbooks	Set of custom Ansible playbooks .yaml used for the automated deployment of applications/components
codeco-exp-framework/cluster_deployment.sh	Core script for Dockerfile generation, Infrastructure Manager enabler, etc.
codeco-exp-framework/install-cluster.sh	Generic cluster installation script
codeco-exp-framework/install-edgenet-cluster.sh	Installation of EdgeNet software script
codeco-exp-framework/install-l2sm-cluster.sh	Installation of L2S-M of the CODECO NetMa component script
codeco-exp-framework/install-acm-cluster.sh	Installation of the CODECO ACM component script
codeco-exp-framework/experiments-net.sh	Complete CNI plugins experimentation script
codeco-exp-framework/create_metrics.sh	Definition of metrics script
codeco-exp-framework/output_results_container.sh	Generation of Latex PDF file for experiments script
edgenet-framework/demo/*	Demonstrations within the EdgeNet testbed
edgenet-framework/tutorials/*	Cluster management .yaml for the EdgeNet testbed
edgenet-framework/installation/*	Core files and .yaml for the installation of the EdgeNet software

4.2.1.2 Installing and Running Experiments

CoDEF provides an easy-to-deploy and easy-to-experiment solution for both CODECO partners and external users (e.g., user DEV) to experiment with CODECO components within different infrastructures (i.e. through the different Infrastructure Managers).

In particular, after following the provided installation guidelines, users can modify and run simple scripts to experiment with the provided features, applications and CODECO components. To run experiments:

- Install the intended [Infrastructure Manager](#) in a machine/testbed following the instructions in the Dockerfile of each Infrastructure Manager.
- Clone the repository to a node/VM that will manage the declarative and seamless deployment of nodes, clusters, and applications across the infrastructure:

```
git clone https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework.git
```


Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- Define the characteristics of the available nodes to be used by the framework (e.g. their IP and MAC as in [example-dhcpd.conf](#) and [example-hosts](#)).
- Create and modify their configuration file(s) as in [example-configuration](#) file to define the characteristics (names, IP, MAC addresses) of the cluster to be deployed.
- Deploy a cluster with user's defined characteristics by modifying and running scripts like the [./install_cluster.sh](#).

As a result, CoDEF will manage the entire experimentation process, facilitating the automated and seamless deployment of nodes, clusters and applications across heterogeneous testbeds and infrastructures. The framework initiates the experiments from scratch, according to the defined parameters, while users can observe the output of the running scripts through the detailed debug messages provided by the Ansible playbook in the terminal (rf. to "Teaser Videos" in the README.md file **Error! Reference source not found.**):

- **deployment of nodes** (e.g. Virtual Machines (VMs)) and Operating System (OS) based on node images; cluster deployment via enabling different [Infrastructure Managers](#) **Error! Reference source not found.** such as on-premise servers with specific hypervisors (e.g., XCP-ng), local VM/cluster deployment using VirtualBox, or cloud systems like CloudLab; number of master and worker nodes with their name, IP and MAC address. The different infrastructure managers need to be installed according to the instructions and enabled/disabled according to the user preference from the [cluster_deployment.sh](#) (i.e. *enable_xcpng_im=true; enable_vbox_im=false; enable_cloudlab_im=false*).
- **Installation of the specified applications and software** (via the Resource Managers and based on [Ansible playbook templates](#)), e.g., K8s configuration (rf to the *K8s_type*, *K8s_networkfabric* parameters in *example-configuration* and *install-cluster.sh* files), applications and CODECO components (rf to the *app_names* and *app_scopes* parameters);
- **Execution of experiments based on defined metrics** (via the Experiment Controller), using similar scripts such as the [create_metrics.sh](#) script.
- **Acquisition and procession of results** (via the Results Processor) e.g., automated Latex-based PDF creation with the [output_results_container.sh](#) script.

4.2.1.3 CODEF and the CODECO Framework

At the current stage of release (v2.0 of the CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit), CoDEF does not yet integrate all the CODECO framework. Instead, users can experiment with individual CODECO components which are defined in the *app_name* field of the installation scripts. CODEF supports the following features:

- Supports the installation of the ACM component which in turn will manage the interconnection and deployment of the rest of CODECO components as described in the CODECO architectural workflow (rf. to D10 [1]),
- Integrates NetMA L2S-M.
- Provides an upgrade to the current EdgeNet software. By replacing the *app_name* with the name of the defined application or CODECO component, as defined in the custom Ansible playbook YAML files (in [codeco-experimentation-framework/playbooks](#)), CoDEF deploys a K8s cluster from scratch with the application or the CODECO component deployed within the cluster.

For example, by running the following scripts, a K8s cluster with the L2S-M solution and another with the ACM component (the current version) will be deployed based on the respective playbook YAML files:

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- **Installation of L2S-M:** [./install-l2sm-cluster.sh](#)
- **Installation of the ACM component:** [./install-acm-cluster.sh](#)

CoDEF continues to be developed by partner ATH and is expected to integrate the global CODECO framework (OSS Basic Toolkit v2.0) and evaluate them in terms of performance and resource utilization under various conditions, e.g. loads and constrains.

4.2.1.4 Experimentation with EdgeNet

4.2.1.4.1 Interconnecting with the EdgeNet Testbed

Focusing on the EdgeNet testbed, CoDEF integrates some .yaml files defining resources to enable the utilization of a shared cluster, under the “installation/[demo](#)” and “installation/[tutorials](#)” directories, respectively. The applicability of these examples relies on the status of the EdgeNet testbed.” directories, respectively. The applicability of these examples relies on the status of the EdgeNet testbed.

- In the first demo (i.e. [cdnserviceexample.yaml](#)), EdgeNet utilizes its Selective Deployment feature to select some nodes from pre-specified geographic locations, as explicitly defined by a selector in the corresponding .yaml file, to run a simple Content Delivery Network (CDN) service.
- In the second demo (i.e. [ping-me-example.yaml](#)), based on the location-based node selection, as defined by the selector in the .yaml file, EdgeNet selects nodes to ping a server or IP address, aiming to generate traffic. This example highlights the potential use of EdgeNet as a benchmarking tool for the CODECO use cases, i.e., setting up clients (around the globe) to assess the provided services.

4.2.1.4.2 Upgraded EdgeNet

CoDEF provides an upgraded version of the open-source EdgeNet software to deploy CODECO-EdgeNet clusters that support fundamental EdgeNet features such as the: i) *multi-provider*, to contribute nodes (VMs/physical machines) into a unified CODECO-EdgeNet cluster with a simple bootstrap script; and ii) *multi-tenancy*, to enable the utilization of a shared cluster with functionalities designed to serve different cluster management purposes such as tenant and role requests, slices and sub-namespaces.

During the CoDEF setup effort, CODECO contributed with minor bug fixes and improvements to the code from the official EdgeNet GitHub repository, enhancing the overall functionality of the infrastructure. We focus on the “[installation](#)” folder which refers to the EdgeNet software utilization.

A step-by-step guide on how to create a local EdgeNet node based on this forked EdgeNet version is provided. In the present document, there are references to the following link⁶¹ as CODECO-EdgeNet and to the following link⁶² as CODECO-EdgeNet-node.

Pre-requisites

For starters, users must:

61 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework/-/tree/main/edgenet-framework/installation/edgenet>

62 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework/-/tree/main/edgenet-framework/installation/node>

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

- Have the CoDEF and *kubectI* installed.

```
git clone https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework.git
```

Instructions to run:

1. **Run** the following script located within the [codeco-experimentation-framework](#) repository. Keep in mind to **modify** the script by defining the specific cluster details to be deployed in the [configurations](#) folder.

```
cd codeco-experimentation-framework/  
./install-edgenet-cluster.sh
```

In the [installation](#) folder of the CODECO-EdgeNet repository, users can find the *.sh* scripts and *.yaml* files after running the *./install-edgenet-cluster.sh* script.

2. After the EdgeNet installation, a [vpnpeer.yaml](#) file is automatically created in both master and worker node(s).
3. Copy the *vpnpeer.yaml* of the worker node(s) into the master node.
4. **Apply** the copied *yaml*(s).

```
kubectl apply -f vpnpeer.yaml
```

5. **Confirm** the node(s) in the cluster.

```
kubectl get vpnpeers
```

4.2.1.4.2.1 EdgeNet User & Namespace Setup – Multi-tenancy

Having deployed the CODECO-EdgeNet cluster with the [./install-edgenet-cluster.sh](#) script from the CODECO Experimentation Framework, it is feasible to create a new “regular” user with limited rights and, afterwards, assign them with roles and rights for various cluster management purposes.

1. **Create a regular user running the [create-user.sh](#)** script which is automatically created and can be found in the [installation](#) folder. It will create a username whose name is the provided email and a respective namespace. In addition, a private key for the user will be created as well as a role-binding request, a user certification folder in the home directory and a configuration file.

```
cd edgenet-framework/installation  
./create-user.sh
```

2. One can **identify the different rights** of the “admin” and “regular user” by **changing the configuration file** located in the *.kube/* directory of the master node and observe the cluster resources (e.g., pods). Rename the configuration files, or add the `--kubeconfig <config-user@gmail.com> -n <namespace>` parameters when executing the commands

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

3. The **rights of the regular user** (e.g. to observe and edit the cluster resources) can be **changed** by applying the appropriate yaml – e.g. make the regular user a [tenant](#) and **approving the request as admins**, adding "approved: true" under the "spec" field.

```
kubectl create -f tenantrequest.yaml --kubeconfig <config-  
user@gmail.com> -n <namespace>  
kubectl edit tenantrequest.yaml
```

Note that when creating the tenant request regular users **must use create** and not apply as they only have “write” and not “read” privileges.

4.2.1.4.2.2 Node contributions – Multi-provider

In order to contribute a node to the CODECO-EdgeNet cluster, a user should:

1. **Copy** the `config-public` file found in the `.kube/` directory into the CODECO-EdgeNet repository i.e. [edgenet/configs/public_ehome.cfg](#):

```
cat .kube/config-public  
pico edgenet/configs/public_ehome.cfg
```

2. Find the public key which was generated on the master node

```
cat .ssh/id_rsa.pub
```

3. **Copy the public key into the CODECO-EdgeNet-node repository** in `vars/edgenet-codeco.yml` and replace the last line named `edgenet_ssh_public_key` so any node can be contributed and can join the cluster. The [edgenet-codeco.yml](#) is located under the `vars` directory.

4. **Establish a connection** to the node intended to be contributed to the cluster e.g.

```
ssh <user@<IP.address>
```

5. Clone the CODECO-EdgeNet-node repository into the node to be contributed

```
git clone <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-  
labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-  
demonstrations/experimentation-framework.git
```

6. **Run the `start.sh` script** which will install Ansible and run the node ansible-playbook on the target machines and automatically deploy an EdgeNet node.

```
cd edgenet-framework/installation/node  
./start.sh
```

7. **Confirm** that the nodes joined the cluster (expected output shown below). **Establish a connection** to the master node:

```
kubectl get nodes -o wide
```


Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

5 Continuous Integration, Testing, Deployment Preparation and Releasing

This section provides an overview on the integration of the CODECO components, as well as an overview on the CODECO methodology, environment and structure that is being used for continuous integration, system testing and deployment preparation and release, based on OSS practices.

The official CODECO repository is provided by partner Eclipse ([CODECO Eclipse GitLab](#)). However, **during the initial stages of development**, for testing and integration of the overall framework, the consortium agreed in addition to consider the [offered ICOM infrastructure](#), which had the capability to support continuous integration with a high degree of automation, from the beginning, while it could be easily connected with GitLab Runners, hosted within ICOM facilities too.

At the moment, the official (public) and private CODECO repositories are synced. Partners push their code directly to the Eclipse CODECO Repository, and GitLab Runners are fully incorporated to the repository for automated testing, building, and deployment of the components to the connected Integration Cluster (provided by IBM). In addition, the private repository hosted by ICOM is still utilized as it provides an intermediate private Container Registry using Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines.

As described in this section, the process of work is as follows:

- CODECO partners upload their OSS contributions (sub-component level) to the official CODECO repository. New commits/merges enable CI/CD Pipelines, as designed by the designated partners in the `gitlab-ci.yml` file of the repository.
- The ICOM GitLab environment is used to support continuous integration, assisting in a faster deployment of all CODECO components and interfaces.
- The overall process is described in the next subsections, where more details for the CI/CD procedures followed, are explained in Section 5.2.1.

5.1 Application Workloads

To experiment with CODECO, it is necessary to consider examples of application workloads. This section provides some information on the application workloads provided in CODECO.

5.1.1 CODECO Dummy Application Workload

In the CODECO operator (ACM) a [demo CR](#) has been inspired by the [Skupper Hello World](#) example. The provided demo CR showcases a seamless data-sharing process between a front-end and back-end application, using the CODECO ACM and SWM components, to transfer the data. The demo highlights how the system handles different application workloads efficiently. The front-end application, responsible for user interactions, generated network-intensive workloads as it communicated with the backend. The backend, which processed and stored the data in a database, managed compute-intensive and I/O-intensive workloads, ensuring quick data processing and efficient database operations. Throughout the demo, our components maintained robust communication and data integrity, demonstrating the system's capability to handle complex, real-world application workloads with high performance and reliability.

5.1.2 CODECO Use-case P5 Application Workload

The CODECO P5 use-cases has as basis a design where Automated Mobile Robots expected to handle goods within a factory warehouse are being subject to remote control. CODECO as orchestration framework is expected to be used to assist in a better distribution of the overall application workload required for AMRs /AGVs to handle they tasks, reducing the required energy expenditure and eventually improving latency (time to completion). The use-case is described in the [CODECO D8 deliverable](#). The Application Workload has been defined by partner FOR based on its local cluster, for which a representation is provided in Figure 31. The overall requirements in terms of hardware and software for the application workload setup is available in the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab, Use-cases, [P5-AMR-Manufacturing](#). The focus is on an application workload developed for Mobile Automated Robots (MARs) and is based on RoS2.

Figure 31: CODECO Use-case P5 Application Workload.

The application workload of P5 corresponds to an application to allow MARs to perform a series of operations and is composed of several images, namely: **Bringup** (activation); **Waypoint follower** (guide a robot manually); **SLAM** (define the map of the robot); **Nav2** (provides the automated MAR navigation).

The user is provided with an adaptation of the CAM for the specific application workload.

5.2 Testing, Deployment Preparation and Releasing

CODECO adopted a continuous integration-system testing/deployment-release methodology, to allow for a release of results in the form of software.

An important part of this methodology regards testing, as it is crucial to identify and fix bugs early and to ensure that the software meets the agreed requirements. Specifically, testing includes the following:

- **Feature – Unit Testing.** Unit testing involves testing internal CODECO sub-components by simulating or mocking all the other components in the framework. This practice enables early detection of failures caused by changes in specific parts of the code or

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

functions. Developers conduct unit testing locally in their development environments, and these tests are also automatically invoked by the Continuous Integration (CI) server. The development teams create the necessary job definitions for use by the CI/CD server.

- **Interfacing – Integration Testing.** Integration testing verifies the proper functioning of a service and its features by examining the seamless interaction of subsystems, while simulating only other services. All CODECO components and sub-components need to successfully pass the integration tests specified before releasing a new software version. Development teams provide instructions on accessing their components' interfaces and functionalities for testing purposes, as well as instruction on how these components can be deployed. Such tests are triggered automatically by the Continuous Integration server for components with updated dependencies.
- **System testing,** which involves deploying all components and assessing fundamental features and user interactions. The purpose of system testing is to evaluate the compliance of the integrated system with the specified requirements. CODECO deployment and testing are also expected to be viable at a global scale by integrating CODECO with EdgeNet. As an enhancement of the initial experimentation approach which intended to be achieved by integrating CODECO with the EdgeNet testbed and attempting to avoid potential bottlenecks for the experimentation, the CODEF was designed within the WP5. This experimental asset, whose details are in subsection 5.2.1 and D10, provides a comprehensive approach for experimenting and testing CODECO components in a declarative and automative manner, across heterogeneous multi-cluster and multi-domain environments. Therefore, CODEF supports but is not limited by the utilization of the EdgeNet software. In this way, CODECO assets will be deployed in K8s clusters comprising geographically distributed nodes (e.g., by testing CODECO using different Infrastructure Managers or utilizing EdgeNet's features such as Multi-provider or Selective Deployment). Experimenters can explicitly define the requirements of the K8s cluster on which they desire to deploy and assess CODECO components. In a later project stage, the system testing will be enhanced by implementing a designated controller, which will allow for the automated deployment of CODECO assets across the testbed infrastructure.

Additionally, preparation of the deployment of the CODECO framework requires its own set of actions:

- Having ensured that automatic testing is taking place in every repository, **manual testing** and **code review** is also crucial to prepare for a successful deployment. Each component leader in CODECO is responsible to review and potentially merge the different repository branches. The Deployment of every sub-component of the CODECO project is individually deployed and assessed **by multiple contributors** to catch potential issues.
- **Documentation** is, also, crucial to prepare for a successful deployment and release of a project like CODECO, where many partner organizations and individual contributors are involved. To address this need, each repository includes proper documentation and readme file featuring **installation guides**, and **usage examples**.
- **Build and Packaging:** It is, also, important to automate and standardize the **build process** to ensure it is reproducible across different environments. For this reason, every subcomponent leader is responsible to package the repository's software into Docker images, to facilitate easy distribution and installation of CODECO components by users and contributors. Every repository includes the appropriate Dockerfiles and/or Makefiles to make the building of the repository reproducible.
- To ensure **Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD), GitLab CI/CD pipelines** have been set up by partner ICOM to automate the testing and deployment processes.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

The final stage in the CODECO OSS lifecycle is the **Software Release** process. CODECO adopted semantic **versioning** to manage the release versions systematically. The last major release was v1.0.0, where the current release is tagged as **2.0.0**. Thus, a new tag has been created out of the main branches of the CODECO project repositories. Additionally, all latest docker images are pushed to the [CODECO dockerHub repository, hecodeco](#) tagged as v2.0.0.

5.2.1 Deployment and CI/CD Methodology

5.2.1.1 Deployment

As described and explained across sections 2 and 3, the CODECO OSS Toolkits follow a modular design, involving different communicating and yet independent components. Moreover, each CODECO component consists of one or more sub-components.

Each CODECO sub-component is encapsulated in a container image to be deployed independently in the form of a K8s deployment object. In case it acts as a K8s controller, the deployment of the container image, requires also to apply the respective CRDs. Containerization enables the packaging of applications into containers, ensuring secure and isolated execution. This facilitates portability across various computing environments, regardless of the specific hardware and operating system being used.

Based on each component's detailed documentation and installation guide, we deployed the whole CODECO framework on our custom K8s Cluster to ensure that all components are properly integrated. On top of that, we deployed a simple *CodecoApp* comprising of a frontend and a backend, as prepared by the ACM team. This was tested by multiple partners, as well, to ensure reproducibility.

An example for the represented deployment of the respective K8s pods is provided in Figure 32 and Figure 33.

NAMESPACE	NAME	READY	STATUS	RESTARTS	AGE
default	acm-swm-app-backend	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
default	acm-swm-app-front-end	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
default	l2sm-controller-5f756fbc5-f6tcc	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
default	l2sm-operator-7494dfbc89-5f8gx	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
default	l2sm-switch-fsmdq	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
default	l2sm-switch-kpzmt	1/1	Running	2 (2d5h ago)	11d
default	l2sm-switch-qsnqk	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-acm	acm-controller-6498f4bcc4-4w5rz	1/1	Running	9 (2m1s ago)	11d
he-codeco-acm	acm-operator-controller-manager-6ffddb99b-484mc	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-api-0	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-controller-0	1/1	Running	9 (2m37s ago)	11d
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-controller-575cf76b99-r7xwj	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-kafka-0	1/1	Running	8 (112s ago)	11d
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-kafka-provisioning-j4vsw	0/1	Completed	0	11d
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-neo4j-0	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-zookeeper-0	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-netma	netma-controller-6cf9d68f68-tm45h	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-pdlc	gnn-controller-f958d5885-q2k54	1/1	Running	15 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-ca-bb4478488-gqf8x	1/1	Running	74 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-dp-664b645d4f-fx7gx	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-inference-5b964c98d8-sw7vc	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-rl-5f8d9c5bf4-wx1ss	1/1	Running	12 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-swm	controller-manager-867fb5fd86-qlr5d	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
he-codeco-swm	solver-d8b666649-g22mx	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d

Figure 32: Deployed K8s pods.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

kube-system	coredns-787d4945fb-578rq	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	coredns-787d4945fb-p42kz	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	etcd-kind-control-plane	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kindnet-5zqr9	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kindnet-pbdp8	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kindnet-wsbgn	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-apiserver-kind-control-plane	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-cni-install-ds-6mp9x	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-cni-install-ds-d9v45	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-cni-install-ds-mx9bd	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-controller-manager-kind-control-plane	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-multus-ds-6g6cb	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-multus-ds-9nzj6	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-multus-ds-r9gqr	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-proxy-56jg6	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-proxy-6nchn	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-proxy-lcgns	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	kube-scheduler-kind-control-plane	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	nodedaemon-49p8l	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	nodedaemon-msmbv	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	nodedaemon-xdfb6	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
kube-system	qos-scheduler-d9d4489d7-j56bt	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
local-path-storage	local-path-provisioner-6bd6454576-vr9rb	1/1	Running	5 (2m44s ago)	11d
monitoring	alertmanager-main-0	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	alertmanager-main-1	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	alertmanager-main-2	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	blackbox-exporter-5b85f4854d-fvctb	3/3	Running	9 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	grafana-b8b78f5-vxlt4	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	kube-state-metrics-64bc777d44-kj9xr	3/3	Running	12 (2m37s ago)	11d
monitoring	node-exporter-2vv7k	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	node-exporter-mwbcr	2/2	Running	7 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	node-exporter-z9wkp	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	prometheus-adapter-7585f5c8bc-n9l47	1/1	Running	5 (2m35s ago)	11d
monitoring	prometheus-adapter-7585f5c8bc-pcq8p	1/1	Running	5 (2m45s ago)	11d
monitoring	prometheus-k8s-0	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	prometheus-k8s-1	2/2	Running	6 (3m40s ago)	11d
monitoring	prometheus-operator-6bb97db7f4-5km52	2/2	Running	7 (3m40s ago)	11d
network-demo-namespace	network-topology-68d879b749-mqmt6	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d
network-k8s-namespace	network-base-745f7bc8cd-w4grl	1/1	Running	3 (3m40s ago)	11d

Figure 33: Deployed Pods in K8s.

5.2.1.2 CI/CD Methodology

GitLab Runners have been set up by partner ICOM in the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab research project](#). Gitlab Runners are located on an ICOM-hosted server and interact directly with the CI Cluster. The CODECO GitLab also utilizes the private Container Registry hosted by ICOM, for the purpose of building images during CI/CD jobs.

The [CODECO ICOM private GitLab environment](#) is fully aligned with the official CODECO Eclipse GitLab structure. The code is available to the consortium and EC representatives.

In addition, within each CODECO sub-component a Dockerfile is provided to build the Docker images of the CODECO services. The Dockerfile of each CODECO sub-component is then be used to automatically build the images within Gitlab CI. Developers can configure the respective gitlab-ci.yml files to automate the tasks of building, testing, packaging, and deploying artifacts on the integration testbed K8s cluster. If any tests or builds encounter failures, the CI server notifies the respective developer to address the issues, through an email. In addition, GitLab container registry is used to share and rebuild container images and perform automated deployment.

Every subcomponent leader is responsible to create a .gitlab-ci.yml file at the root of the repository. This file contains stages such as build, test, and deploy, and specified jobs within each stage. These jobs are designed to run scripts for building the code, running the previously mentioned automated tests, and deploying to the designated CI Cluster. ICOM ensures that pipelines are triggered on every commit, merge request, or tag creation, providing continuous feedback on code quality. **GitLab's environment variables** are used to manage sensitive data securely and connect the repositories to an intermediate **private Container Registry** to save images during building stages. All the different CI/CD processes run on

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Gitlab Runners hosted by ICOM. This setup enables consistent, repeatable processes and helps catch issues early, ensuring smoother deployments and higher code quality.

The `gitlab-ci.yml` files follow a structure like in [p3-mec-enablement/.gitlab-ci.yml](https://p3-mec-enablement.gitlab.io/.gitlab-ci.yml)

Container orchestration is done based on K8s. The K8s deployment YAML configuration files (including Secret, Services, Volumes etc.) are managed by ICOM as the integration leader (WP3, T3.6) with the help of each component’s development team.

Currently, when the code is uploaded (in each subcomponent) and all the tests are executed successfully, a merge request is sent by the contributor to the sub-component leader (task leader), to update the main branch of each project within CODECO public repo. At the end of each implementation cycle, a new tag is created, and a new code version, utilizing the tag, is published/ released, using only the code that is available in the “main” branch of each CODECO subcomponent. Moreover, at the end of each implementation cycle, the images of subcomponent are uploaded to the [CODECO dockerHub, hecodeco](https://hub.docker.com/u/codeco). More details regarding the release version of each subcomponent are provided in Annex II.

5.2.2 Integration and Testing Facilities

CODECO is relying on different types of testbeds as provided in Table 33, to achieve specific integration and experimentation targets:

- Individual testbeds provided by individually partners (local use).
- A common Cloud-based infrastructure is being set for the consortium (rf. to D10 for details), with the focus to allow for federated, multi-tenant integration and experimentation.
- On other large-scale Edge-Cloud experimentation environments, such as EdgeNet.

Table 33: Status of the CODECO proposed integration and testing facilities.

Testbed type	Target	Status
Local-use testbeds	To allow individual partners to test CODECO in alignment with the CODECO use-cases	Individual partners such as FOR, ATH, TID, I2CAT have developed specific local-use testbeds. Some of these testbeds are expected to be interconnected – rf. to D10 for details.
ICOM private K8s cluster	To allow for integration and system tests of the overall CODECO framework since an early stage of the project	ICOM has provided the cluster and performed the required testing for the release of the CODECO sub-components (early release CODECO Basic Operation Toolkit v0.1)
Shared Cloud-infrastructure	To allow the consortium to perform integration and experimentation in federated, multi-tenant environments.	Rf. to D10 for details on status, configuration, minimum requirements, etc.
CODEF and EdgeNet	Validate CODECO components and assist in the exploitation of CODECO across diverse / heterogeneous infrastructures in a declarative and automated manner. Provide a starting point for multi-cluster, multi-tenant experiments, interconnected over the Internet	The CODEF asset, not initially planned, provides a way to circumvent some issues found with EdgeNet (federated clusters’ orchestration issues), and provides the means to experiment with CODECO across different environments, e.g., EdgeNet, CloudLab.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

5.2.2.1 ICOM Private K8s Cluster

At the current stage of the project, ICOM K8s cluster is used for integration tests. As mentioned in the previous subsection, GitLab Runners running at integration testbed K8s cluster provided by ICOM, take charge of executing the CI/CD pipelines, as they described in the “gitlab-ci.yml” file, to automate the procedures of testing, building, packaging and deployment. For the resource monitoring of the cluster, K8s Dashboard, Prometheus and Grafana, are configured and utilized, providing valuable insights on the health status of each CODECO component.

In detail, ICOM K8s cluster consists of a single K8s node with the following characteristics, ensuring that the hardware requirements of CODECO components can be fulfilled:

Operating System: Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS
CPU: 2 x Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4214 CPU @ 2.20GHz
Memory (RAM): 128GB
Hard disks: Total Drives: 3 x 960GB, RAID 5

6 Summary and Next Steps

D12 corresponds to the final release of the CODECO OSS Basic Operation toolkit, and this report is a companion report to the software that has been released (v2.0). In addition to the support to the deployment and experimentation with CODECO, this report provides an overview on the experimentation assisted developments and on the continuous integration, testing, and deployment processes.

The work presented in D12 aimed to facilitate the development, integration, and deployment of the CODECO framework following an incremental approach, by presenting tools adopted to support the defined implementation workflow and integration framework, coding guidelines, installation instructions, as well as inputs and outputs of each CODECO sub-component, ensuring the coordination of the work between consortium members belonging to different organizations and external developers.

The next steps are the following:

- The integration coordinated work developed in WP3, T3.6 under the leadership of ICOM will be continued on the second phase of the project in WP4, T4.4 (ICOM), thus assuring continuity of all the effort developed.
- The next steps focus on i) ensuring a timely resolution of all open issues still detected in the current code; ii) targeting federated, multi-tenant cluster operation in an automated way (WP4).
- In this context, the coordination of the integration in the CODECO shared Cloud infrastructure to perform continuous integration will also be continued in articulation between WP4 (T4.4) and WP5.

7 References

- [1] N. Psaromanolakis (Ed.). CODECO D11 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v1.0. November 2023.
- [2] R. C. Sofia (Ed.). CODECO Deliverable D10 -Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design v1.0, June 2024.
- [3] R. C. Sofia (Ed) CODECO Deliverable D9 -Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design v1.0. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8143860>.
- [4] R. C. Sofia, J. Soldatos (Ed). “A vision on Smart, Decentralised Edge Computing Research Directions”. Sep 2021. NGIoT white paper, DOI [10.5281/zenodo.5837299](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5837299).
- [5] R. Sousa (Ed), CODECO D8 - Fine-grained Use-case Design and Business Impact (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8143800>.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Annex I – Summary of Code Open Issues

Table 34: CODECO OSS Basic Operation Toolkit v2.0, summary of open issues.

Component	ID	Description
ACM	ACM-OI-1	Developer dashboard for user interaction with CAM.
	ACM-OI-2	Integration with NetMa (Nemesys)
	ACM-OI-3	Integration of the NetMA network performance metrics in the CAM status.
NetMA	NetMA-OI-1	Close the internal integration in a unified way. Currently each component has one interface (Prometheus, API/rest) to expose the metrics, but the idea is to integrate all the metrics in a unified way as described in Error! Reference source not found.. Expected Deadline: M20.
	NetMA -OI-2	There is a need of unification, synchronization and automatization of Network probes. It should be realized an integration process to achieve this even though the main goal will be to have independent and customizable probes. This open issue will have two main lines: to consolidate the common data model for all probes and to select/manage the probes to be used during compilation time. Expected Deadline: M20.
	NetMA -OI-3	Automatization of NetMA deployment in an integrated way: Having a unique deployment configuration file with the different parameters and commands needed to deploy each NetMA sub-component. <u>Expected Deadline: M23.</u>
	NetMA -OI-4	Worst case scenario. We are currently testing the main workflow, but we need also to define how to act if there are complications or failures, both internal and external. <u>Expected Deadline: M23.</u>
PDLC	PDLC-OI-1	Currently, CODECO metrics status is overseen via a transient approach. However, over time and based on the needs of PDLC, this situation may adapt to consider long-term state.
	PDLC-OI-2	Provide an implementation of PDLC-CA directly feeding a K8s scheduler (implement interface I-PDLC-SWM-1)
	PDLC-OI-3	Perform model training within CODECO framework with all CODECO metrics in use (node and link).
	PDLC-OI-4	Provide a PDLC implementation where sub-components can reside on different nodes
	PDLC-OI-5	Create MLOps pipeline for the PDLC-RL model
	PDLC-OI-6	Implement pending interfaces between PDLC and other CODECO components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I-PDLC-SWM-1 I-PDLC-NetMA-1 (optional)
	PDLC-OI-7	Update RL and GNNs model designs to remove dependency on number of nodes in the cluster
SWM	SW-OI-1	Implement the re-scheduling of applications. Expected deadline: M22.

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

Annex II – Release Versioning

Table 35 provides a list of the current CODECO sub-components, URLs for open-source code, and images in Docker. The notation in the Table is as follows:

- **C**: CODECO component acronym.
- **SC**: Sub-component abbreviation.
- **OSS**: GitLab Repo URL for the open-source code.
- **DH URL**: URL for the respective Docker Hub image.
- **Tag**: Image tag.

Table 35: CODECO sub-components.

C	SC	URL	OSS	DH URL	Tag
ACM	ACM Operator	https://gitlab.eclipse-se.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/acm/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/acm-controller	hecodeco/acm-controller:2.0.0
PDLC	PDLC-DL-MLOps	https://gitlab.eclipse-se.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/mlops	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/mlops/releases/2.0.0	-	-
	PDLC-DL-GNNs	https://gitlab.eclipse-se.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-gnns/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-controller	hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-controller:2.0.0
				https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/pdlc-dl-gnns-stggn-inference	
	PDLC-DL-RL	https://gitlab.eclipse-se.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-DL/pdlc-rl/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/pdlc-rl-inference	hecodeco/pdlc-rl-inference:2.0.0
PDLC-CA	https://gitlab.eclipse-se.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-CA	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/PDLC-CA/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/pdlc-ca	hecodeco/pdlc-ca:2.0.0	

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

C	SC	URL	OSS	DH URL	Tag
		decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca	learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-ca/-/releases/2.0.0		
	PDLC-DP	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-dp/-/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/pdlc-dp	hecodeco/pdlc-dp:2.0.0
	PDLC-Deployment	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/privacy-preserving-decentralised-learning-and-context-awareness-pdlc/pdlc-deployment/-/releases/2.0.0	-	
SWM	QoS Scheduler	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/qos-scheduler/-/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/swm-scheduler	hecodeco/swm-scheduler:2.0.0
	Workflow Placement Solver	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/scheduling-and-workload-migration-swm/workload-placement-solver/-/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/swm-solved	hecodeco/swm-solved:2.0.0
				https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/swm-controller	hecodeco/swm-controller:2.0.0
NetMA	Network Exposure	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-exposure	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-exposure/-/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/layes/hecodeco/netma-networkexposure/	hecodeco/netma-networkexposure:2.0.0

Grant Agreement nr: 101092696

C	SC	URL	OSS	DH URL	Tag
	Network State Management	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/network-state-management/-/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/netma-netmanagement	hecodeco/netma-netmanagement:2.0.0
	Secure Connectivity	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/secure-connectivity	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/network-management-and-adaptation-netma/secure-connectivity/-/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/l2sm-controller	hecodeco/l2sm-controller:2.0.0
				https://hub.docker.com/r/alexdec/l2sm-controller-manager	hecodeco/l2sm-controller-manager:2.0.0
				https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/l2sm-operator	hecodeco/l2sm-operator:2.0.0
				https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/l2sm-switch	hecodeco/l2sm-switch:2.0.0
MDM	Connectors	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/connectors	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/connectors/-/releases/2.0.0	-	-
	Graph db	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/graphdb/-/releases/2.0.0	-	-
	MDM API	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/metadata-manager-mdm/mdm-api/-/releases/2.0.0	https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/mdm-controller	hecodeco/mdm-controller:2.0.0
https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/mdm-api				hecodeco/mdm-api:2.0.0	
				https://hub.docker.com/r/hecodeco/mdm-neo4j-ctrl	hecodeco/mdm-neo4j-ctrl:2.0.0

